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**QUALITY OF LIFE AND COMPLIANCE AMONG MOTHERS ON A CONDITIONAL
CASH TRANSFER PROGRAM IN A MUNICIPALITY OF LAGUNA, PHILIPPINES**

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Acceptance Page:

This Special Project titled: **“QUALITY OF LIFE AND COMPLIANCE AMONG MOTHERS ON A CONDITIONAL CASH TRANSFER PROGRAM IN A MUNICIPALITY OF LAGUNA, PHILIPPINES”** is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Course.

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Biographical Sketch

Jenzer Mae A. Ambrocio received a Bachelor of Science in Nursing from Far Eastern University – Manila in 2009. After graduating, she was hired by the Department of Labor and Employment under their "NARS Program" and was deployed in the local community and local hospital for six months. It was a challenge for her to apply and be accepted for a job because during those years, there was an oversupply of nursing graduates in the Philippines. She has also volunteered in various private and public medical institutions. Since the nursing career was a bit elusive for her due to the difficulty of being accepted by hospitals at that time, she tried to apply when a job vacancy in the Department of Social Welfare and Development arose. She was hired in 2012 and was also deployed in the local community. Since then, helping the vulnerable and disadvantaged households has become one of her main tasks, which of course through the help of the Department's program. The said program is focused on a holistic approach that includes health, nutrition, education etc. The department also gives her the the opportunity to help different groups of people in the society such as women, senior citizens, PWDs, typhoon victims, and even those who are affected by volcanic eruptions. She is still affiliated with DSWD up to now. She also applies what she learned as a nurse by imparting knowledge to the people in her workplace. Her current work is more focused on social services. She considers this job a great blessing to her because it gives her the ability to reach out to our underprivileged countrymen.

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very supportive parents, Jeany Ambrocio and Eliezer Ambrocio who supported her all throughout her life. Their love and encouragement lifted her spirit during those times that she wanted to quit. Her parents' love is incomparable, she is forever grateful for having them. Also, to her beautiful sister, Je-Ann Grace Ambrocio who also gave her support and never left her side, especially during those days when stress arose.

She also likes to give special thanks to her husband, Adriene "Unmyeong" Quizon and his family for their continuous support and understanding during my endeavor. Adriene's love, support, comfort, encouragement, kisses, hugs, supers, and eyeballs helped her a lot, especially in times that she did not want to continue anymore. She wanted to express her gratitude to him for being by her side through thick and thin, for being her research assistant, and for giving her all the help she needed. His prayer sustained her.

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Dedication

I dedicate this thesis to all my loved ones and to those people who supported and believed in me.

First, to my parents Jeany Ambrocio and Eliezer Ambrocio, who supported me in all the aspects of my life. Thank you very much, “Mi” and “Pa” for always guiding me, for supporting my studies, for being there in good and bad times. I am always grateful to have you both! I love you so much!

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I would also like to dedicate this research study to all my friends, colleagues, program beneficiaries, parent leaders, LGU officials and staff, regional staff, and to all the people who have given me their support for this study.

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Abstract

This study explores the pursuit of a good quality of life and the crucial role of government policies in achieving this aspiration. It begins by acknowledging the universal desire for a comfortable and satisfying quality of life, which encompasses good health, strong family bonds, a balanced environment, and a peaceful society. The 1987 Philippine Constitution, particularly Section 9 of Article II, underscores the government's responsibility to promote a just and dynamic social order that uplifts the nation's prosperity and independence while eradicating poverty.

Despite its natural wealth, the Philippines faces persistent poverty, with causes including low economic growth, limited employment opportunities, high inflation, and a burgeoning population. The United Nations has cited the country for having one of Asia's highest poverty rates. Poverty's impact on households is far-reaching, affecting access to education, healthcare, housing, and basic sustenance.

In response, the Philippine government introduced the *Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino* Program (4Ps) in 2009, a conditional cash transfer initiative aimed at addressing poverty. Evaluative studies have shown positive outcomes, including improved healthcare for pregnant women and young children, increased educational participation, reduced child labor, and heightened community engagement.

This study delves into the impact of 4Ps on the quality of life of beneficiaries, specifically mothers, and how compliance with program conditions influences their well-being. The research questions explore compliance levels with program conditions and the quality of life in terms of physical health, psychological well-being, social relationships, and the environment. Additionally, the study investigates potential differences in quality of life based on demographic profiles and compliance.

The hypotheses suggest significant differences in quality of life concerning demographic factors and between compliant and non-compliant mothers. The study holds significance for various stakeholders, including mothers and families who stand to benefit from increased compliance, nursing practice by emphasizing preventive healthcare, CCT implementers in enhancing compliance, and future researchers using this study as a reference.

The study was conducted in a Municipality in the Province of Laguna from November to December 2020, employing descriptive correlational research methods, including documentary analysis and questionnaires. A total of 303 mother-grantees were randomly selected, with inclusion criteria based on registration dates within a specified timeframe. The scope includes compliance with program conditions related to family development sessions, child health monitoring, school attendance, and community involvement. Quality of life assessment covers four domains using the WHO QOL-BREF questionnaire, with language translation considerations.

In summary, this study aims to learn the impact of compliance with 4Ps program conditions on the quality of life of mothers, shedding light on the role of conditional cash transfers in improving well-being and contributing to poverty alleviation in the Philippines.

Chapter I

THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

Background of the Study

Everyone dreams of living a good and happy life. Who would not want a comfortable and satisfying quality of life? Good health, strong family relations, balanced environment and peaceful society are some that may constitute a pleasant living. While it may be an individual effort to strive harder to continuously improve one's level of well-being, the State in general and the government in particular help in ensuring that such aspiration will be realized. In fact, Section 9 of Article II of the 1987 Philippine Constitution mandates that:

“The State shall promote a just and dynamic social order that will ensure the prosperity and independence of the nation and free the people from poverty through policies that provide adequate social services, promote full employment, a rising standard of living, and an improved quality of life for all.”

This legal provision is a gentle reminder to all public officials to always put the best interest of the citizens above all. Hence, measures that would potentially counter the impediments of having quality life must be bolstered. This is particularly true since poverty remains an important challenge in the country which has been significantly linked to having poor quality of life (Park, Turnbull & Turnbull, 2002; Lam, Guo, Wong, Yu & Fung, 2017).

According to Asian Development Bank (2009), poverty in the Philippines is primarily caused by low to moderate economic growth, weakness in employment generation, high inflation, and high levels of population. The country was even

reported by the United Nations to have one of the highest poverty rates in Asia despite its natural resources and biodiversity (Marrone, 2016). In fact, in September 2017, the survey of the Social Weather Stations (SWS) revealed that 47% of the general Filipino families consider themselves as poor, a finding that was 3% higher from the results obtained in June of the same year (Cepeda, 2017). This translates to about 10.9 million families who tagged themselves as poor.

Much has been said about the effects that poverty poses to affected households. At the very least, poor families cannot afford to send the young children to school until they finish complete basic education as they cannot support their daily school expenses; they also cannot avail adequate clothing and proper housing to shield them from the changing environments; they cannot prioritize the health needs of the family members especially when some get sick or are hospitalized; and even worse, some cannot sustain the daily meals that are supposed to fuel them for their activities of daily living. All these circumstances undeniably lead to an unfavorable quality of life, contrary to what the Constitution assures of the public. It is in the light of these observations and experiences that the national government is likewise challenged to uphold the status of living of the marginalized and disadvantaged sectors of society if descent and comfortable living are to be attained. This may involve policymakers' call on passing reforms and bills that would merit people's increased access to basic services such as education, health, transportation, and infrastructure.

In the Philippines, the national government adopted the conditional cash transfer (CCT) program in 2009, commonly known as *Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino* Program (4Ps) as one of its flagship anti-poverty programs. It is being executed under the management of the Department of Social Welfare and Development in partnership

with other National Government Agencies, the Local Government Units and Civil Society Organizations. The CCT in the Philippines helps to fulfill the country's commitment to meet 5 out of 8 Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) such as to Eradicate Extreme Poverty and Hunger, Achieve Universal Primary Education, Promote Gender Equality, Reduce Child Mortality, and Improve Maternal Health. This is also in consonance with the mandates of the United Nations as expressed in Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Running for about nine years, several evaluative studies on its impact were conducted. For instance, Frufonga (2015) noted a significant improvement in the preventive healthcare and nutritional status among pregnant women and younger children, increased participation rate in education, decreased dropout rate due to decreased incidence of child labor and more visible community involvement among the parents. He added that the program has helped in changing the expenditure pattern of poor families by allocating the largest amount of their financial assistance for food, education, medicine or hospitalization and savings thereby keeping their members healthy and well. Improvement in the access to health services particularly those relating to maternal and child such as prenatal, antenatal, and postnatal check-ups; delivery attended by skilled professionals and vaccination of both the pregnant and the newborn was also observed (Glassman, et al., 2013). Given that such variables are part of the general quality of life, it may be assumed that poverty-reduction programs like the 4Ps help in advancing one's quality of life. In fact, Ferreira and colleagues concluded that efficient implementation of the CCT program in Brazil (i.e., Bolsa Familia) promotes positive quality of life among its covered beneficiaries.

On the other hand, since 4Ps operates on a conditional cash transfer scheme,

it may be worth knowing how compliance to set program conditions affect the perceived benefits and impact to quality of life of the program among its beneficiaries. This is very timely since the program has encountered challenges in meeting the target compliance rate of at least 96% for education and health and at least 95% for family development session (FDS). In fact, for the months of August and September 2018, average compliance rates of 93.78%, 92.89% and 90.26% for education, health and FDS respectively were noted in the province of Laguna, all of which are below the benchmark set. In the municipality of Magdalena, the challenge is even greater as compliance rates for the same period were lower compared to the provincial accomplishment at 89.96%, 90% and 88.53% for education, health and FDS respectively (Department of Social Welfare and Development CaLaBaRZon, 2018).

Since full benefits of the program are only experienced when the households comply to all conditions of the program as determined through systematic monitoring, it may be assumed that those highly compliant households will exhibit better quality of life compared to their non-compliant counterparts. This is also in support to the conclusion of Son (2008) who stressed that conditionality is crucial in any CCT program if both short-term and long-term objectives are to be attained. Accordingly, compliance to conditions is one factor that drives the CCT recipients to maximize their opportunity to access offered services especially those relating to education, health, and community involvement. In fact, in the study of Velarde & Fernandez (2011) about the welfare and distributional impacts of 4Ps, they concluded that increasing the compliance rate to program conditions would equate to increased poverty-reducing impacts of the program to its recipients.

In the light of the foregoing observations, the current study would like to look

into the potential difference in the quality of life among the 4Ps beneficiaries, particularly the mothers when their extent of compliance to set conditions is taken into account.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to determine if there is a significant difference in the quality of life of compliant and non-compliant mothers under a conditional cash transfer program. Specifically, the study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the extent of compliance of the respondents to program conditions with respect to:
 - a. attendance to Family Development Session;
 - b. periodic health monitoring of 0-5 years old children;
 - c. deworming of elementary children;
 - d. attendance to school of 3-18 years old children; and
 - e. participation to community activities?
 - f. What is the level of quality of life of the respondents in terms of:
 - g. physical health;
 - h. psychological health;
 - i. social relationships; and
 - j. environment?
2. Is there a significant difference in the quality of life of the respondents with respect to their profile?
3. Is there a significant difference in the quality of life of the respondents in terms of their compliance?

Research Hypothesis

H1: There is a significant difference in the quality of life of the respondents with respect to their profile.

H2: There is a significant difference in the quality of life of compliant and non-compliant mothers

Significance of the Study

Mothers and Family - The findings of this study will help increase awareness among the CCT recipients as to the added benefit that they will get should they faithfully comply with the conditions of the program. It will help them realize how increasing their access to basic services such as quality education and health impact their perception of general well-being and life satisfaction. Finally, findings will make them more appreciative as program recipients especially that not all poor households were included in this CCT.

Nursing Practice - This study will reinforce the role of nurses, particularly those engaged in the field of community health nursing in health promotion aspect. Specifically, preventive health check-up and monitoring may be continuously advocated especially among the vulnerable population groups including the children and pregnant women.

CCT Implementers - The findings of this study will help the frontline agents of CCT to bolster their efforts in encouraging and attaining high compliance rates across all program conditions. Most especially that one of the goals of the program is to uplift the level of well-being of its beneficiaries, this study hopes to affirm the view that CCT does not only provide cash grants to poor families but also helps them achieve a

satisfying life in the long run.

Future Researchers - This study will serve as reference for other researchers who are interested in studying the quality of life of beneficiaries under a CCT program. They may be able to utilize the data and findings of this study for further development and improvements in the formulation of interventions for health of the poorest households and pertinent policy suggestions on CCT implementation. They may also learn from the strategy used in this research, difficulty encountered during its conduct, statistical methods employed and other things that would potentially help them in their future investigation.

Scope and Delimitations

This study aimed to determine the quality of life of compliant and non-compliant mothers under a conditional cash transfer program. It also covered the moderating effects of the respondents' age, educational attainment, and duration of membership in the CCT program. Data collection procedure was conducted from November to December 2020 in a Municipality in the Province of Laguna.

A descriptive correlational research study was employed to meet the research objectives. Specifically, documentary analysis was performed in order to determine the extent of compliance to program conditions of the respondents. On the other hand, an adapted questionnaire was used to measure the level of quality of life of the respondents, with a separate section asking for their demographic information. Towards this end, a total of 303 mother-grantees were randomly selected as respondents of the study. However, only those beneficiaries who were registered in the municipality from the year 2012 to January 2015 were included in the sampling. Those who transferred in from other municipalities, provinces or regions during this

period were also included. On the other hand, those who cannot read and understand instructions stated in the questionnaires were not included in the sampling of respondents or they can be included if there is someone who will assist on answering the questionnaire.

For the extent of compliance to program conditions, this was limited to the respondents' attendance to monthly family development sessions, preventive health check-up of their 0-5 years old children, school attendance of their 3-18 years old children, and participation to monthly community activity. This variable did not include other condition of the program such as compliance to the monthly health monitoring of pregnant women since not all households had pregnant member in the past. In fact, only few pregnancies were recorded and monitored since the inception of CCT program in the locality. Moreover, their records of compliance were limited only from January 2016 to January 2019.

For the level of quality of life (QOL), all four domains of the World Health Organization (WHO) QOL-BREF questionnaire were covered such as the physical health, psychological health, social relationships, and environment. However, one limitation of this instrument is the unavailability of questionnaire in Filipino language. Hence, the instrument was translated into a language that is suitable to the level of understanding of the respondents which may affect its established psychometric properties.

Operational Definition

Quality of life - refers to the "individuals' perceptions of their position in life in the context of the culture and value systems in which they live and in relation to their goals, expectations, standards and concerns" (WHO, n.d.). This will be measured using the

WHOQOL-BREF questionnaire.

Physical health – refers to the domain of QOL that measures activities of daily living, dependence on medicinal substances and medical aids, energy and fatigue, mobility, pain and discomfort, sleep and rest, work capacity.

Psychological health - denotes the domain of QOL that measures body image and appearance, negative feelings, positive feelings, self-esteem, spirituality/religion/personal beliefs, thinking, learning, memory, and concentration.

Social relationships - refers to the domain of QOL that assesses the aspects of personal relationships, social support, and sexual activity.

Environment – pertains to the domain of QOL that determines aspects of financial resources, freedom, physical and security, health and social care, accessibility and quality, home environment, opportunities for acquiring new information and skills, participation in and opportunities for recreation/leisure activities, physical environment, and transport.

Family Development Session - refers to the 2-hour learning session being attended by 4Ps grantees on a monthly basis.

Periodic health monitoring - equates to the preventive health check-up of children aged 0-5 years such as height and weight monitoring, nutritional status assessment and immunization.

Deworming - pertains to the administration of deworming pills to elementary children twice a year by the Department of Education.

School attendance – denotes the 85% minimum monthly attendance of children aged

3-18 years based on the actual number of school days.

Community activity - pertains to the monthly participation of 4Ps grantees in productive tasks such as clean-up drive of the barangay, *Brigada-eskwela*, cultivation of communal gardens and other activities as directed by their municipal link.

Chapter II

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Review of Related Literature

This chapter contains discussion of concepts related to the variables of the study. It also contains discussion regarding the Conditional Cash Transfer. Concepts related to the independent variable will be discussed first followed by those pertaining to the dependent variable.

Conditional Cash Transfer Program in the Philippines

The Philippines' conditional cash transfer is also known as *Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino* Program (formerly Bangon Pamilyang Pilipino) and it operates under Department of Social Welfare and Development. According to the article the program seeks to eliminate extreme poverty in the Philippines by spending in health and education particularly in ages 0–18. *Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino* Program is patterned on programs in other developing nations like Brazil (Bolsa Familia) and Mexico (Oportunidades). As of June 25, 2014, the *Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino* Program has 4,090,667 household beneficiaries and was operating in 17 regions and 79 provinces.

The *Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino* Program or the Conditional Cash transfer of the Philippines was patterned by the Department of Social Welfare and Development in the conditional cash transfer system from Brazil and Mexico by John Gerald B. Santiago. The DSWD originally tested this initiative in 2007, in the municipalities of Sibagat and Esperanza in Agusan del Sur; Lopez Jaena and Bonifacio in Misamis Occidental, the Caraga Region; and Pasay and Caloocan, with a budget of only 50 million pesos. As stated in the article, Santiago and Samantha Vizconde renamed the

program *Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino* Program (4Ps) on July 16, 2008, by administrative order number 16, series of 2008 and established implementing instructions. It is the primary poverty alleviation program of former President Gloria Macapagal-administration. The initiative aims to educate many Filipino children from pre-school to secondary school by providing them with daily allowances while they attend their regular lessons. Their parents appreciate the program since their children learn a lot in class and they are provided nutritional allowances for their children's food when they attend school. The program has two goals. The first is social development, in which they invest in capability building to break the intergenerational poverty cycle, and the second is social assistance, in which they provide monetary support to address short-term financial needs.

In the Philippines, *Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino* Program (4Ps) as a poverty-reduction strategy has been implemented since 2008 among selected pilot areas in the country with particular emphasis on both social assistance and social development. The program was conceived out of the objective to break the intergenerational cycle of poverty among the poorest of the poor households by giving cash grants that are conditional to the compliance of beneficiaries. These include attendance to Family Development Session (FDS) once a month, regular monitoring of children aged 0-5 years and pregnant women based on Department of Health (DOH) protocols and receiving deworming pills twice a year for children at the elementary level for the households to receive their health grants and compliance to at least 85% monthly school attendance of children age 3 to 14 years for them to receive their education grants. With the massive expansion of the program in 2012, coverage of children in education was increased to 18 years old.

For successful compliance to these conditions, each household receives 500 pesos health grant per month, 300 pesos education grant per month per child enrolled in day care centers and elementary schools and 500 pesos education grant per month for those children enrolled in junior high school and 700 for senior high school. However, only a maximum of three (3) children must be selected for compliance monitoring. The said package of grants is viewed to be relatively generous compared to CCT programs of other countries (World Bank, 2014). Regarded as one of the fastest rising CCT programs in the world, 4Ps became the cornerstone of the Philippine government's social protection efforts (World Bank, 2014). Thereafter, attempts to evaluate its effectiveness and impact were performed through scientific and empirical studies considering the huge number of resources that the government invests in its nationwide implementation (Orbeta, 2014; Orbeta & Pacqueo, 2016).

In the second wave evaluation of the program in which a regression continuity design was employed such that 4Ps beneficiaries were compared to non-poor households, Orbeta (2014) found out that the program is keeping on its claims. For one, 4Ps pregnant women were found to be more inclined with timely monitoring of their health conditions and ultimately deliver in health facilities such as lying-in clinics and hospitals compared to their non-4Ps counterpart. The study revealed that 70% of childbirth among 4Ps mothers were attended by qualified health personnel, higher than the 55% recorded rate by NSO in 2013 covering the general population. There was also a significant difference in the number of children who received vitamin A, iron supplementation and deworming pills at 86%, 35% and 79% respectively. However, there was no difference noted in the medicine and food expenditure of the 4Ps and non-4Ps households, a finding that is in contrast with another empirical study of Tutor (2014) and Frunfonga (2015) about the impact of 4Ps on consumption and general

well-being respectively.

In terms of education, Orbeta (2014) found out that the enrollment rate was found to be significantly higher especially among older children aged 12-15 years old with 6% difference from their non-4Ps counterparts. Attendance of children to day care centers and kindergarten was found to be almost double compared to non-4Ps poor children. This may be attributed to other finding in which the education expenditure of 4Ps households was found to be 82% higher compared to non-4Ps households making the needed supplies and learning aids available to the students. On the other hand, there appears no significant difference in the attendance of children to at least 85% of the monthly school days among elementary and high school levels.

Guidelines on the Implementation of *Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino* Program

The rationale for this program, according to the Department of Social Welfare and Development's Administrative Order No. 16 Series of 2008, is that the Conditional Cash Transfer Program in Latin American and Caribbean countries such as Mexico, Brazil, Honduras, Jamaica, and Nicaragua in the late 1990s demonstrated effectiveness in promoting human capital accumulation among poor households. There is also substantial evidence of efficacy in increasing enrollment rates, enhancing preventative health care, and increasing household intake of nutrient dense foods. The program gives financial grants to low-income families so that they can invest in human capital by sending their children to school and taking them to health facilities for preventive health checks. The Philippine government, under the direction of the Department of Social Welfare and Development, was challenged to imitate or adopt the Conditional Cash Transfer (CCT) Program dubbed *Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino* Program to address health and educational matters/issues, as well as the rising

incidence of poverty, which continues to distress extremely poor Filipino families. The primary goal of the Program is to encourage change to break the intergenerational cycle of poverty. In terms of behavior, parents were encouraged to invest in their children's (and their own) futures (health, nutrition, and education) because low school enrollment and high malnutrition rates are intimately linked to the poverty cycle in the Philippines. It is also mentioned that well-designed and efficient program processes and mechanics are essential to serve as guides to local implementers for the program to be implemented properly.

The *Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino* Program is being implemented in compliance with the Millennium Development Goals such as eradicating extreme poverty and hunger, obtain universal primary education, lower child mortality, improved maternal health empowering women, and gender equality must be fostered. The Department of Social Welfare and Development is one of the government institutions committed to implementing the *Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino* Program in order to attain the Millennium Development Goals. Executive Order No. 221 of 2003, Amending Executive Order No. 15, Series of 1998, titled "Redirecting the Functions and Operations of the Department of Welfare and Development," mandates the DSWD to provide assistance to government Units (LGUs), non-government organizations (NGOs), other national government agencies (NGAs), people's organizations (PCs), and other members of civil society in effectively implementing programs, projects, and services that will alleviate poverty and empower people.

According to the Administrative Order, the *Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino* Program is a poverty reduction approach that provides cash grants to extremely impoverished households to enable family members to meet particular human

development targets. It focuses on developing the human capital of the poorest families (health/nutrition and education) because low school enrollment and malnutrition rates are intimately linked to the poverty cycle in the Philippines.

The program's purpose is to market human capital among disadvantaged families, particularly children, to break the intergenerational cycle of poverty. The goals are to improve preventive health care for pregnant women and young children, increase elementary school enrollment/attendance, reduce child labor, increase consumption of nutrient dense foods in poor households, encourage parents to invest in their children's (and their own) future, and encourage parent participation in the growth and development of young children, as well as community involvement.

RA 11310/ 4Ps Law

On April 17, 2019, President Duterte signed Republic Act No. 11310, often known as the 4Ps Act. He signed the bill knowing that the state's responsibility is to "promote a just and dynamic social order, thereby lifting its citizens and marginalized sectors out of poverty through policies that provide adequate social services, promote full employment, a rising standard of living, and an improved quality of life for all." According to the law, the CCT provides financial subsidies to impoverished households for a maximum of seven years to enhance their health, nutrition, and education. Under unusual circumstances, the National Advisory Council (NAC) may recommend a longer duration. (4Ps Law, 2019)

Through the *Listahanan* Program, the Department of Social Welfare and Development selects suitable household-beneficiaries of the 4Ps utilizing a standardized targeting system. Beneficiaries will be revalidated every three years on a regular basis. According to the law, homeless families, farmers, fisherfolks,

indigenous peoples, those in the informal settler sector, and other people in geographically isolated and disadvantaged areas, including those without electricity, are eligible beneficiaries and will be automatically included in the DSWD's standardized targeting system.

Households must meet the following conditions in order to be eligible for cash grants: they must be classified as poor or near-poor based on the Standardized Targeting System and the poverty threshold issued by the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA) at the time of selection, they must have members aged zero (0) to eighteen (18) years old or be pregnant at the time of registration, and they must be willing to comply with the conditions specified.

The Advisory Council shall determine the amount of conditional cash transfer to beneficiaries in accordance with Section 7 of the 4Ps law, using the following schemes: (a) Conditional cash transfer grant per child enrolled in day care and elementary programs shall not be less than 300 pesos (300.00) per month per child for a maximum of ten months per year or annum; (b) Conditional cash transfer grant per child enrolled in junior high school shall not be less than 300 pesos (300.00); (c) The conditional cash transfer grant per child enrolled in senior high school shall not be less than seven hundred pesos (700.00) per month per child, with a maximum of ten months per year; and (d) The health and nutrition grant shall not be less than seven hundred fifty pesos (750.00) per month, with a maximum of twelve months per year.

The law also states that the health/nutrition grant component aims to promote healthy practices and family development, improve the health and nutritional status of pregnant and post-partum mothers, infants, and young children, and increase the utilization of health services by the household-beneficiary. The health grant is a fixed

amount that is not affected by the number of people in the home. According to the law, all beneficiaries identified by the standardized targeting system as qualified household-beneficiaries of the 4Ps will be automatically covered by the National Health Insurance Program. The funds required for his or her coverage will be derived from revenue collected through Republic Act No. 10351, popularly known as the "Sin Tax Reform Act of 2012."

According to the law, the Philippine Institute for Development Studies will conduct an impact assessment every three years after the Act goes into effect, and they will evaluate the effectiveness of the 4Ps, program implementation, and the veracity of the list of household-beneficiaries. According to the 4Ps law, pregnant women must receive pre-natal services, give birth in a health facility attended by a skilled health professional, and receive post-partum care and post-natal care for her newborn; and children aged zero to five years must receive regular preventive health and nutrition services, including check-ups and vaccinations.

Children one to fourteen years old must receive deworming pills at least twice a year, children three to four years old must attend day care or pre-school classes at least eighty-five percent (85%) of the time, children five to eighteen years old must attend elementary or secondary classes at least eighty-five percent (85%) of the time, and at least one responsible person or grantee must attend/ be present at least one responsible person or grantee must attend/ be present at least one responsible person or grantee

Compliance to Program Conditions

The conditional cash transfer (CCT) program is a poverty-reduction strategy that provides cash grants to identified poor families and households in exchange for

compliance with certain verifiable conditions. Unlike dole-out programs, CCTs are typically linked to conditions that aim to improve beneficiaries' access to and utilization of basic services, particularly those related to health and education (Philippine Institute for Development Studies [PIDS], 2007).

Ibarraran and his colleagues (2017) defined conditionalities in the context of CCT programs as "behaviors that favor the accumulation of human capital in the children of beneficiary households, thereby increasing their ability to generate income in the future and helping to break the intergenerational transmission of poverty" (p. 35). This means that beneficiaries must be motivated to make certain behavioral changes before cash transfers can be made (Son, 2008). As a result, compliance with these conditions is a critical factor in the program's ability to achieve both its short-term goal of increasing household capacity to purchase needed goods and services and its long-term goal of human capital formation by focusing specifically on children's knowledge and skills through sound education (Rawlings & Rubio, 2003).

PIDS (2007) emphasized the importance of conditions in a CCT program such as the country's *Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino* Program (4Ps). As a result, adhering to these conditions helps to break the natural tendency of parents to underinvest in their children's human capital. Granting them a large sum of money will undoubtedly help them overcome the normal costs of daily living, but it will not guarantee an improvement in the children's education or health status because they are free to spend these funds on whatever they deem most important. As a result, conditions were set up so that some out-of-pocket expenses, such as school supplies and transportation, would also be covered. Compliance with these conditions eventually enables parents to support how their children become future agents of economic

change in their respective households. Households that meet these criteria are assumed to be breaking the inherent intergenerational cycle of poverty and achieving greater opportunities and equality in the community (Cruz, De Moura & Neto, 2017).

On the other hand, some consider the imposition of conditions in CCTs to be demeaning to the beneficiaries because the government and implementing agencies appear to require them to do things against their will. Furthermore, monitoring beneficiaries' compliance incurs significant administrative costs. In fact, it was discovered that compliance monitoring accounts for approximately 9% and 2% of total administrative costs in the implementation of CCTs in Honduras and Mexico, respectively. As a result, others believe it is appropriate to simply provide financial assistance to qualified poor households and rely on their commitment to spend the money on useful and productive activities.

However, it was generally discovered that the costs associated with rigorous compliance monitoring were outweighed by the benefits obtained from CCT programs (Son, 2008). Proper compliance monitoring leads to "more effective coordination in the planning and implementation of measures to strengthen the supply of health and education services for the poorest, as well as significant progress on information systems and the use of data to inform policy decisions" (Ibarraran et al., 2017).

Finally, it was suggested that countries that consider CCTs as an intervention to alleviate poverty keep the component of conditionalities that are relevant and responsive to the needs of the poor with a cost-effective monitoring scheme, as this has been shown to help a great deal in the achievement of program goals (Son, 2008; Ibarraran, et al., 2017). Furthermore, imposing such conditions encourages families and the government to share responsibility and commitment to increasing the human

capital of children and adolescents (Ibarraran, et al., 2017).

Different CCT programs have their own set of grants and conditions that covered beneficiaries must meet, even though they all share the common goal of assisting the marginalized sector to eventually live free of poverty (Rawlings & Rubio, 2003). Ibarraran and colleagues (2017), on the other hand, suggested general criteria to be followed when designing sets of conditions to be monitored. These include compliance with verifiable behaviors, objective and easy-to-measure variables, and sector priorities that limit human capital growth, which may vary from one area to the next.

This feature is thought to ensure positive compliance among beneficiaries because the actions they must take are beneficial to them and contribute to addressing the problems that plague poor households.

In terms of the implementation of *Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps)* in the country, different results are available pertinent to the compliance of beneficiaries to set conditionalities. In the report of DSWD Field Office CARAGA in 2012, high compliance rate was noted across all program conditions. Specifically, 98% of the children aged 3 to 14 years were found to comply with the 85% minimum monthly school attendance. Such success in compliance was attributed to findings gathered from interviews among parents in which the importance of the education grants was underscored in helping them purchase basic supplies and materials for their children's schooling. In terms of the *Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps)* implementation in the country, various results are available regarding beneficiary compliance with set conditions. In 2012, the DSWD Field Office CARAGA reported a high compliance rate across all program conditions. Specifically, 98% of children aged

3 to 14 years were found to follow the 85% minimum monthly school attendance requirement. Such compliance success was attributed to findings from parent interviews in which the importance of the education grants was emphasized in assisting them in purchasing basic supplies and materials for their children's schooling was emphasized.

Similarly, in the areas of health and nutrition, a high 97% compliance rate was recorded, implying that children aged 0 to 5 years and pregnant women were subjected to periodic health status monitoring. Finally, there was a significant increase in parent attendance at their monthly family development session (FDS), which has helped them gain self-confidence and a sense of empowerment (Barcelon, 2012).

On the other hand, there appears to be a disparity in some sources regarding the impact of the 4Ps on compliance and observed behavioral changes. For example, the Commission on Audit (COA; 2017) revealed that while compliance on health conditions was reported to be as high as 99% in deworming and 96% in immunization of children 0-5 years and regular check-ups of pregnant women in 2016, spot checks performed by Social Weather Stations after being commissioned by DSWD revealed 11% cases of underweight children and that only 21% of the surveyed women gave birth to proper hygienic children.

Alarmingly, such cases of non-compliance with program conditions were discovered to be related to beneficiaries' lack of adequate information about their shared responsibility as part of the program. As a result, COA proposed that longitudinal studies be conducted in order to better capture the impact of 4Ps in bootstrapping beneficiaries out of poverty, especially given that the program has been running in its pilot municipalities for eight (8) years.

Quality of Life

Health Organization as "individuals' perceptions of their position in life in the context of the culture and value systems in which they live and in relation to their goals, expectations, standards, and concerns." This definition adheres to the position that QoL encompasses various domains of living that may include physical, social, psychological, and environmental, which at times makes this construct difficult to measure scientifically (Theofilou, 2013). In fact, QoL may include aspects of "emotional, economic, and physical well-being, interpersonal relationships, personal development, self-determination, social inclusion, and rights," though there is no clear consensus among scientists on what constitutes QoL. (Maestro-Gonzales, et al., 2018). However, it appears that the majority, if not all, of the researchers in this field agree that QoL is influenced by both internal or subjective and external or objective factors (Ferriss, 2004).

Though closely related, QoL should not be confused with standard of living, which is primarily defined by the amount an individual earns (ScienceDaily, n.d.). It should instead consider one's physical and mental health, the environment, education, recreation and leisure time, and social belonging. Similarly, QoL should not be interpreted solely as referring to one's level of well-being. Smith (1973; cited in Theofilou, 2013) emphasized that "well-being should be used to refer to objective life conditions that apply to a population as a whole, whereas quality of life should be limited to individuals' subjective assessments of their lives."

However, the academic and scientific communities began to blur the distinction between these two distinct but related concepts, and QoL is now used to refer to both objective and subjective assessments and evaluations that an individual assigns to life

experiences and situations (Campbell, Converse & Rogers, 1976; as cited in Theofilou, 2013).

QoL is multidimensional and, to some extent, subjective, as it is influenced by a person's life experiences (Jenkinson, n. d.). For example, a healthy and happily married person may suddenly report a low quality of life after losing a job. In contrast, a disabled person who has not faced significant challenges in the last few months may report a high quality of life despite his physical limitations. This supports the notion that QoL is determined by multiple dimensions rather than a single aspect of life.

According to Barcaccia and colleagues (2013), QoL as a multidimensional and dynamic concept encompasses life domains such as life satisfaction, which is highly subjective and may fluctuate; physical health, psychological state, level of independence, family, education, wealth, religious beliefs, a sense of optimism, local services and transportation, employment, social relationships, housing and the environment; cultural beliefs and affiliations.

Various researchers in fields ranging from healthcare to social sciences exhibited grown up interest in the study of quality of life because of increased awareness to social issues and challenges. Park, Turnbull, and Turnbull (2002) discovered that poverty has a negative impact on several domains of a family's QoL, including health, productivity, physical environment, emotional well-being, and family interaction. In terms of health, they noted that poverty contributes to hunger, undernutrition among pregnant women, and limited access to healthcare services, all of which prevent poor families from reaching their full potential.

When it comes to productivity, it was discovered that children's opportunities for maximum learning were hampered, as were family leisure and recreational activities, which resulted in lower life satisfaction. The negative effects of poverty on the physical environment of households were discovered to be unsafe and unfavorable home environment and neighborhood. This translates to a lack of access to basic services such as safe drinking water, electricity, and adequate housing materials, as well as an increased vulnerability to violence and crimes.

In terms of emotional well-being, they reported that poor families, both adults and children, are more likely to experience stress, anxiety, and depression because of financial insecurity, particularly when bills are already past due. Such circumstances eventually lead to lower self-esteem among family members. Finally, financial difficulties impair family interaction, as evidenced by low quality parent-child bonding and positive responses to children's dependency needs. This includes an irritable and uneasy atmosphere, especially when money is discussed, which frequently leads to marital conflicts and even parent-child arguments. Several policy recommendations have been made considering the established relationship between poverty and QoL in various domains.

In a study on the relationship between QoL and the human development index (HDI) conducted by Kooh, Nedjat, Yaseri, and Cheraghi (2017), they discovered a positive association in which the mean scores of QoL significantly increase as the HDI increases in terms of physical health, psychological health, and social relationships using WHOQOL-BREF. In their study, HDI was defined in terms of life expectancy, expected years of schooling for children, and the country's gross national income per capita. Further research revealed that the QoL of people in developing countries is

significantly lower than that of people in developed countries.

This was especially true in the physical, psychological, and environmental QoL domains. In the domain of social relationships, however, no difference was observed. Finally, they concluded that HDI can be used to predict QoL. As a result, they recommended that the government invest in improving HDI determinants such as strengthened health promotion and illness prevention in order to "increase life expectancy, improve educational status, and raise monthly incomes," particularly among the most vulnerable segments of society.

Individuals' QoL is influenced by their health, which is defined as more than just the absence of disease. Many studies have been conducted in the past, particularly using tools that measure health-related quality of life (HRQoL; Megari, 2013; Ofquila, Ybanez, Llamedo, & Hermogenes, 2016). However, few studies have attempted to measure the impact of health concerns such as illnesses on the general QoL of the target subjects, which encompasses broader concepts and domains of living (Wikman, Wardle & Steptoe, 2011).

Wikman and colleagues (2011) conducted a cross-sectional population-based study on the quality of life and affective well-being of middle-aged and older adults with chronic illness in this regard. Diabetes, chronic lung disease, asthma, cancer, osteoarthritis, rheumatoid arthritis, coronary heart disease, and stroke were discovered to significantly impair various aspects of QoL and affective well-being, though the impact of observed impairments varies depending on the number of comorbidities the respondent has. Stroke survivors had the lowest QoL, followed by chronic lung disease, rheumatoid arthritis, coronary heart disease, diabetes, and asthma. It was also discovered that the quality of life of adults suffering from cancer

and osteoarthritis was the least affected.

Nonetheless, they concluded that "the presence of chronic illness is associated with significantly lower general QOL and happiness, as well as higher levels of depressed mood across a wide range of conditions," confirming the notion that the negative impact of such chronic diseases extends beyond function-related impairment (Walker, 2007; as cited in Wikman, 2011).

In the Philippines, individuals' perception of QoL is largely influenced by the changes encountered in the community that may include housing conditions, access to basic services such as water, electricity and shelter and programs that directly affect education and health. In the report published by Numbeo in 2018 about the QoL in the country, moderate QoL was noted when indices related to gaining control, welfare, healthcare, environment, cost of living, property price to income ratio, road traffic travel time and smog are accounted.

Individuals' perceptions of QoL in the Philippines are heavily influenced by changes in the community, which may include housing conditions, access to basic services such as water, electricity, and shelter, and programs that directly affect education and health. When purchasing power, safety, healthcare, climate, cost of living, property price to income ratio, traffic commute time, and pollution are all considered in Numbeo's 2018 report on QoL in the country, moderate QoL is noted.

Purchasing power, healthcare, and property price to income ratio indices were reported to be very low, high, and very high, respectively. This means that most households in the country are struggling to meet their basic needs due to rising commodity prices and the relatively low wages they receive. Such findings are consistent with those of the Asian Development Bank (ADB; 2009), which highlighted

poverty as a persistent challenge despite the country's recent moderate economic growth. As a result, if inclusive growth and development are to be achieved, it appears critical to effectively implement ongoing and proposed poverty-reduction programs.

According to the Social Progress Imperative (as cited in ABS-CBN News, 2015), the Philippines had a social progress score index of only 65.46, which is equivalent to "medium low," placing the country in 64th place globally. This translates to the country's standard of living in terms of basic human needs, opportunities, and well-being foundations. Access to water, shelter, medical care, safety, knowledge, information, education, personal rights, and freedom were among the factors evaluated.

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Indeed, the Philippines was found to have the most room for improvement in terms of access to advanced education, personal safety, and ecosystem sustainability. In comparison to other countries with comparable GDP per capita, the country performed poorly in "perceived criminality, political terror, press freedom index, premature deaths from noncommunicable diseases, obesity rate, water withdrawals as a percentage of resources, tolerance for immigrants, and discrimination and violence against minorities."

A more recent survey conducted by the Social Weather Station in the second quarter of 2018 revealed, on the other hand, that Filipinos in general remain optimistic about their individual quality of life and the country's economic situation in general, despite the belief that they have become poorer compared to the previous year. More specifically, the availability of food on the table was the most pressing concern for these families, prompting them to consider themselves poorer, resulting in a lower quality of life (Mateo, 2018).

Studies on the Impact of Conditional Cash Transfers in other countries

There are many CCT evaluations, many supported experimental designs, and positive short-term impacts in other nations like Latin America, Mexico, and so on. These deal with reducing current poverty, enhancing young children's nutrition and health, and raising older children's academic achievement. (Fiszbein and Schady 2009).

Studies have shown that the majority of CCT programs that combine health and education have positive short-term absolute impacts on school enrollment and attendance for children subject to conditionalities related to education, though the magnitude of those impacts varies depending on the program's characteristics and the population it is intended to serve. (Fiszbein and Schady 2009; Murnane and Ganimian 2014; Glewwe and Muralidharan 2016).

Additionally, there are frequently advantageous effects on academic progress. While these immediate effects are suggestive, they only allow for projections of future long-term gains and thus are unable to offer conclusive proof of the longer-lasting changes that are the ultimate goals of CCTs. The review of the data concerning the long-term effects of Conditional Cash Transfer by the team of T. Millan was supported

in the CCT of Nicaragua. They agreed that the non-experimental matching results demonstrate positive absolute impacts on educational and learning outcomes for both young men and women that are consistent with the experimental effects but larger in magnitude. (Millán et al., 2019)

According to a review of the long-term effects of Conditional Cash Transfer in Honduras, the authors discover significant increases in grade attainment for older (24–26-year-old) indigenous women and non-indigenous women of about half a grade, but not for indigenous men. (Millán et al., 2019)

The analysis of Conditional Cash Transfers' long-term effects conducted by the Millan group in Mexico, Nicaragua, Colombia, Honduras, Ecuador, Cambodia, Pakistan, and Malawi demonstrated that CCT programs lead to better human capital accumulation that extends beyond elementary education. The extent to which these investments result in better market and family-related outcomes or higher lifetime earnings is less certain. Undoubtedly, some studies show detrimental effects on hours worked or participation in the labor market, but these seem to reflect better continued school attendance during young adulthood (and hence arguably could be interpreted as beneficial). In experimental evidence from Nicaragua, positive differential impacts on labor earnings and on off-farm employment were demonstrated. Non-experimental indication of impacts after 10 years or more also implies positive impacts on labor market outcomes in Mexico and Colombia (Familias en Acción). In contrast, experimental evidence from Mexico, Honduras, and Malawi, as well as non-experimental evidence from Ecuador, Cambodia, and Pakistan, failed to demonstrate any discernible improvements in the labor market. (Millán T. et al., 2019).

In a study on the effects of conditional cash transfers on health in various

nations, Gertler 2000 found that the number of daily outpatient visits to medical facilities increased by 2.09 percent in areas where cash transfers were made available to the populace. Based on statistics from health centers in the control and treatment areas, Morris discovered in 2004 that although pre-school children's use of services increased significantly, antenatal care or 10-day postnatal care uptake did not significantly increase. According to mothers' reports, the same program was found to significantly affect antenatal care uptake as well as regular well-child checkups and growth monitoring visits for kids (showed increased by 18, 19 and 15 percentage points respectively).

According to the review, a study from Nicaragua demonstrated a beneficial effect on health care utilization, with an increase in the proportion of infants (0-3 years old) taken to health centers in the previous six months of 19.5 percentage points after one year and 11 after two years (Maluccio, 2004; Lagarde, Haines, & Palmer, 2009)

According to the Journal of Health and Population Study, when they reviewed the various studies on the effects of Conditional Cash Transfer on maternal and newborn health, they discovered that almost all of them pointed to a notable increase in the use of various MNH services, and the results are consistent across different countries. However, the studies' only distinction is in the services they focus on.

The Indian JSY program that has required three or more visits has increased by 11 percentage points, according to the reports. Results also showed that a common service output reported is related to births attended by skilled personnel, where every study had positive and significant effects, ranging from a low of 4 percentage points difference between beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries in Guatemala to a high of 37 percentage points difference in India. Three studies that examined births in medical

facilities came to similar conclusions, demonstrating beneficial and significant effects as well as effect sizes that were significantly larger than those noted for other outputs. A study conducted in Nepal revealed a 4-percentage point difference between beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries (Glassman et al., 2013).

Two studies from Mexico and Uruguay examine the impact of CCT on the prevalence of low birth weight in their review. The proportion of infants born with low birth weight decreased by 4.6% and 1.5%, respectively, in Mexico and Uruguay, according to the article, in both studies that looked at the incidence of low birthweight. Results from Mexico's Oportunidades program regarding the use of contraceptives showed that beneficiaries were 16 percentage points more likely than non-beneficiaries to use a modern contraceptive method.

Another analysis of Mexico's Oportunidades' heterogeneous effects revealed a small and insignificant impact on the use of contraceptives. Results on risky sexual behavior are available for both Oportunidades. According to a study conducted by CCT of Malawi, participants in the program had a 0.29-times lower likelihood of testing HIV-positive. In studies that looked at maternal mortality and fertility, a mixed picture of impact was found. According to a study, changes in the fertility rates of Honduras, Nicaragua, Mexico, and Uruguay have an impact on both the age-specific and overall fertility rates, ranging from a rise of 45 to 1% in Nicaragua. (Glassman et al., 2013).

The review by Glassman & group and the meta-analysis by McGuire, Bach-Mortensen, and Kaiser on the effect of cash transfers on subjective well-being and mental health in low- and middle-income countries revealed that conditional transfers, on average, have a positive effect on recipients' indicators of mental health and subjective well-being. Life satisfaction was used as the outcome indicator, and effects

were greater in cases where the cash transfer was conditional. They conclude that while they only have minor adaptation effects, they have a modest but significant and long-lasting impact on wellbeing. As stated, despite their modest size, reported improvements are a sign of true success if subjective well-being and mental health measure well-being more directly than other indicators. They also noted that conditional transfers might be among the most effective methods of enhancing lives, even if their effect sizes are modest (Glassman et al., 2013).

Synthesis

This chapter enlightens the compliance and the quality of life of compliant and non-compliant mothers in Conditional Cash Transfer Program. *Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino* program has been running for several years in our country and through the effort of our government, a lot of interventions are given to the poor and vulnerable population that may be able to help this sector to attain a better quality of life and to improve their level of wellbeing.

Complying with the program conditions is vital for the beneficiaries and the program. Through their compliance, the beneficiaries are empowered and able to connect with different stakeholders. They can enjoy various benefits by complying with the program conditions and these benefits may be able to create small but significant changes in their lives as well. The Family Development Session was created to address the social needs of the family and is one of the activities in the *Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino* Program's implementation. It takes a big role in this implementation to ensure that every family shall improve their lives and being responsible enough in complying with the settings of the program. If the beneficiaries fulfilled, they would indeed learn a lot in the sessions given by the department. One of the most important

effects of FDS is the behavior change of the beneficiaries. This is quite challenging for the implementers because it will only start when the people realize that there is something that needs to be changed in their current situation. As defined, behavior change is a modification and transformation of human behavior. Through all these things that are fully enjoyed by the beneficiaries, it may be the reason why the other studies similar showed a positive effect on beneficiaries' life.

In complying with program conditions, the program beneficiaries enjoyed the full benefits of the program. Some studies indicate an optimistic outcome on the beneficiaries' condition of life and wellbeing. We might as well assume that if they can get all these benefits such as the services received from health and education, and the knowledge they learn from attending the Family Development Sessions, then these things may bring changes in their lives so they can achieve a good quality of life.

On the other hand, the non-compliant beneficiaries who were unable to get these full benefits may be able to miss certain opportunities that would help them to have a better situation. Change may not come easily especially for those people who are not willing to adjust from their old habits. Some of the beneficiaries are unwilling and resistant to change, but still, the department exerts effort through different interventions.

Since 4Ps works on a conditional cash transfer scheme, it is worth knowing how compliance set program conditions affect the perceived benefits and impact to the quality of life of the program among its beneficiaries. Upon reading the pieces of literature, the program has encountered challenges in meeting the target compliance rate of at least 96% for education and health and at least 95% for Family Development Session (FDS). For the months of August and September 2018, average compliance

rates of 93.78%, 92.89%, and 90.26% for education, health, and FDS respectively were noted in the province of Laguna, all of which are below the benchmark set. In the setting of the study, the challenge is even greater as compliance rates for the same period were lower compared to the provincial accomplishment at 89.96%, 90%, and 88.53% for education, health, and FDS respectively (Department of Social Welfare and Development CaLaBaRZon, 2018).

Based on the review made by the researcher, it has been noted that some of the studies cited bear some similarities and differences to the current study. The current study focused on the compliance and quality of life of mothers on conditional cash transfer. Through the continuous education and value formation of a mother or her husband, parents were expected to be responsible to their children. If they become responsible, they would have a good vision in life and possibly uplift their living condition and perhaps may lead to a better quality of life. In other words, they will no longer depend on government support as they will be able to stand on their own, carry their burden and become empowered in helping their selves.

In the light of the rich findings available in the literature, the current study would like to provide additional knowledge especially on the relationship between poor households' compliance to program conditions and their general quality of life. This is particularly interesting since contradicting findings were noted in previous studies and investigations.

Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored on the theoretical underpinnings of the Change Theory of Kurt Lewin. Lewin's Change Theory on the other hand posits that for positive behavioral change to occur, individuals must undergo three stages namely unfreezing,

changing and refreezing (Hartzell, 2012). While more commonly employed in organizational and corporate contexts, this theory can also be applied in healthcare and community settings (Oguejiofo, 2018).

During the unfreezing stage, customary behaviors, specifically those that are unfavorable to one's health are thawed by making the individuals realize what can be improved from the seemingly status quo being continuously demonstrated. It is in this stage that communication is essential so that awareness can be built among the target individuals. Future interventions will not be effective unless they have realized what needs to be changed and what benefits they can get from taking away such ill practices. This will be followed by the changing or transitioning stage whereby interventions are tried to be embraced. Definitely, this is the period where individuals may experience uncertainty with the new environment and habits they are portraying. Hence, it is important that support networks and implementers of the interventions remain visible to aid in this challenging phase. Constant reminder as to why they chose to engage in such step may be reminded to motivate them towards successful completion and eventual entry to the last stage which is refreezing. In this final stage, newly acquired positive health behaviors are to be cemented in the system on the individuals until these become the new norm or status quo. In order not to lose this change, implementers may use rewards system for continuous demonstration of change in the belief that positively reinforced behaviors are likely to be repeated.

In the current investigation, those CCT program beneficiaries who have been in the non-compliance state for a long period of time who therefore do not adhere to the program's call to invest on the human capital of children may be viewed as individuals who need change toward positive behaviors. Further, it is during the

conduct of case management and FDS of CCT implementers that the change can be introduced. Ultimately, once these partner beneficiaries return to compliance state, proper monitoring must be ensured for them not to revert to previous undesirable behavior. Further, higher level of general quality of life may also indicate successful integration of the planned change among the respondents.

Conceptual Framework

A researcher-made conceptual model shows the interplay between and among the variables involved in the study. As shown in figure 1, there are three important elements in the realization of this study as signified by three large boxes: the independent, dependent, and moderating variables.

The first box presents the independent variables (IV) of the study which is the respondents' compliance to CCT program conditions. The second box contains the dependent variable which is the quality of life. A horizontal line connecting the two boxes signifies possible relationship between the independent and dependent variables. It is assumed that compliance to program conditions has bearing in the quality of life of the respondents. The third box at the lower portion of the model contains the moderating variables of the study such as age, educational attainment, and duration of membership in CCT program. A vertical line connecting the center of the horizontal line and the third box signifies a possible effect of the moderating variables on the relationship between the independent and dependent variables of the study. It is assumed that the profile of the respondents moderates the effects of compliance to program conditions to their quality of life.

Figure 1. Conceptual Model Showing the Effect of Compliance to Program Conditions to the Quality of Life of Mother-grantees on a CCT Program

Chapter III

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This segment discusses the methodology of the investigation. The methodology includes the research design, sampling design, research setting, methods and tools for data collection, ethical considerations, and statistical treatment.

Research Design

This study will utilize a descriptive research design which according to Stangor (2011) aims to create a snapshot of the current state of affairs of the variables being studied. He added that this design offers a fairly accurate depiction of what is happening at any given time.

Specifically, a correlational method will be employed in this study which is used to assess or determine relationship between or among two or more relevant variables (Stangor, 2011). However, this type of method cannot draw inferences about the causal relationships between and among these variables, hence cannot be used to answer questions like why and how (Siddharth, 2011).

A descriptive-correlational research design will be used since the major objective of the study is to determine whether the compliance of mothers to CCT program conditions is related to their health-related quality of life. Further, the current study looks into a possible relationship that exists between the variables involved. Finally, this study does not aim to answer why such relationship exists.

Sampling Design

To meet the objectives of this study, a proportionate stratified random sampling

will be utilized. When the target population is large, this sampling design is frequently used because it involves breaking the population up into smaller groups or strata based on the shared traits of the members. During stratified random sampling, also known as stratification, the strata are created based on the shared traits or characteristics of the members, such as income or level of education. Proportional or quota random sampling are other names for stratified random sampling. (Hayes A., 2020).

Specifically, a lottery method with replacement was performed where the list of all mother-grantees belonging to a CCT program in the locality will be secured. However, those households headed by solo male parents will be excluded from the list as the focus of the study was among mother-grantees. The municipality has 941 active households as of January 2019, there are a total of 775 households headed by mother-grantees. To get the sample they were divided into two subgroups based on their status of compliance to program conditions. This is done in coordination with the Compliance Verification Division, the reference given was from the lists of complaint and non-compliant last January 2019. Two fishbowls separating the compliant from the non-compliant group were made available. For compliant 152 out of 665 households were drawn and for non-compliant 151 out of 276 were drawn as samples. Those mothers that were able to achieve at least 85% compliance rate across all program conditions were included under the compliant group. On the other hand, those that were not able to record at least 85% compliance rate across all program conditions were included under the non-compliant group. In overall 303 mothers under the *Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino* Program will serve as respondents of this research study.

Research Setting

This study was conducted in the town of Magdalena, a 4th class municipality in the fourth district of Laguna province. Located approximately 103 kilometers south of Manila, the town is situated at the foot of Mt. Banahaw that makes the area ideal for agricultural activities such as planting of coconut trees and rootcrops (wowlaguna.com, 2010). Due to its scenic views, the town had been a destination for several local television features and films. St. Mary Magdalene Church is one of its many must-visit attractions along with the Pintong Pilak Cave and Balanac River for its water rafting activities (DILG CaLaBaRZon, 2018). As published in *Biyaheng Laguna* (2014), Magdalena is often called the “Little Hollywood of Laguna.”

In 2017, Magdalena ranked 169th on the cities and municipalities competitiveness index in areas of economic vitality, government productivity infrastructure and resiliency (DTI, 2018). Primarily an agricultural land, a vast area of the municipality is cultivated for rice and other grains. In the same year, Magdalena was recognized as one of the outstanding municipalities to receive the Rice Achievers Award (RAA) for their high yield of rice production and the local government unit’s support to farmers for sustainable production (Department of Agriculture, 2018). Aside from this, the locals of Magdalena also earn from small scale businesses like cottage industries and tourism.

The municipality of Magdalena is politically subdivided into 24 barangays with an estimated population of 25,266 as of May 2015 (DILG CaLaBaRZon, 2018). Of these, there are a total of 922 households covered by the *Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino* Program as of November 2018. 48 of these households are headed by solo parents while 15 are headed by minor grantees with designated guardians (DSWD

CaLaBaRZon, 2018). The CCT in the area started in 2010 with only 326 households registered as the pioneering set. With the Expanded Age Coverage Policy and additional funding of this flagship program, the number of covered beneficiaries in the municipality increased significantly to augment in the education and health-related needs of children age 0 to 18 years old. Indeed, a total of 1,335 students from Day Care to Grade 12 and children age 0-5 years are being monitored for compliance to education and health respectively as of November of 2018. On the other hand, no pregnant woman was eligible for health monitoring for this period. In the year 2018 alone from January to September, a total of approximately 12M pesos cash grants were given to households who were able to comply to the conditions of the program (DSWD CaLaBaRZon, 2018).

Magdalena, Laguna was selected as the setting of this study since the researcher is already familiar with its geographical aspect and the general community residing in it. This is a crucial factor during the data collection procedure where time needs to be maximized to reach the needed number of responses. Moreover, the researcher as a development worker, would like to contribute to the existing literature about the implementation of the *Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino* Program in the locality where she has personal knowledge and years of experiences working in. This helped contextualize the experiences of the respondents in terms of the interpretation of their responses.

Research Instrument and Tools

A combination of adapted questionnaire and documentary analysis was the data gathering tools for this study in order to give answers to the research problems. In particular, documentary analysis was employed to determine the respondents'

extent of compliance to the conditions of *Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino* Program. Documents such as periodic compliance turnout and beneficiary tracking reports were requested from the program's Compliance Verification Division. These documents contain information about the households' compliance to program conditions on a monthly basis as well as the corresponding reasons for non-compliance and interventions rendered by the development worker, as applicable. Finally, the respondents' quality of life was measured using the World Health Organization Quality of Life (WHOQOL-BREF) questionnaire. A separate section on the upper portion of this questionnaire was added in order to get the profile of the respondents namely age, educational attainment and duration of membership in the CCT program. All of the 26 items in WHOQOL-BREF were included in the said data-gathering instrument.

A culturally sensitive international tool for assessing people's quality of life, WHOQOL-BREF gauges how well-off people perceive themselves to be across four main areas: environment, social relationships, psychological health, and physical health (WHO, n.d.). Through confirmatory factor analysis, it was discovered that the 26-item WHOQOL-BREF has good to excellent psychometric properties in terms of internal consistency, item-total correlations, discriminant validity, and construct validity. (Skevington, et al., 2004). Similar findings were noted by Berlin and his colleagues (2005) who stressed that WHOQOL-BREF is a valid and reliable instrument in measuring individuals' quality of life across various settings and cultures. In fact, in its cultural validation in the Philippines, dela Vega (2013) concluded that WHOQOL-BREF "is a statistically and culturally valid tool for measuring quality of life." Specifically, she noted that the instrument has high internal consistency (alpha coefficient = 0.88) and very good concurrent validity with domain scores correlating at 0.001 levels of significance.

Overall, this instrument was composed of two parts. Part 1 pertains to the demographic profile of the respondents such as their age, educational attainment and duration of membership in CCT. Name was also asked but was optional in nature. The second part contains items that measure the level of their quality of life by selecting a score from the range of 1 to 5 as a response to the statement read by the researcher. An example of these items is: “*how safe do you feel in your daily life?*” in which the response may be chosen from the following options:

- | | | |
|---|---|-------------------|
| 1 | - | not at all |
| 2 | - | a little |
| 3 | - | a moderate amount |
| 4 | - | very much |
| 5 | - | extremely |

Verbal Interpretation of Statistical Data:

Legend:

Scale Range	Interpretation	Remarks	Verbal
5	4.20-5.00	Very good (<i>Napakaganda</i>) Very satisfied (<i>Sobrang nasisiyahan</i>)	Very Great Extent
4	3.40-4.19	Good (<i>Mabuti</i>) Satisfied (<i>Nasisiyahan</i>)	Great Extent
3	2.60-3.39	Neither poor nor good (<i>Minsan mahirap minsan hindi</i>) Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied (<i>Minsan nasisiyahan minsan hindi</i>)	Moderately Extent
2	1.80-2.59	Poor (<i>Mahirap</i>) Dissatisfied (<i>Hindi Nasisiyahan</i>)	Low Extent
1	1.00-1.79	Very poor (<i>Sobrang hirap</i>) Very dissatisfied (<i>Sobrang hindi nasisiyahan</i>)	Very Low Extent

Data Gathering Procedure

Upon finalization of the thesis proposal, permission from the Ethics Review Board (ERB) of the University of the Philippines was obtained. In order to gather the

necessary data for this research study, a written request was forwarded to the Office of the Regional Director of the Department of Social Welfare and Development Field Office IV-A through the Provincial Link of Laguna Provincial Operations Office. Copy of the thesis proposal and instrument employed was also provided as required by the Planning and Research Unit. Scope of documentary analysis was also discussed to secure a copy of pertinent records. Similar request to conduct a study was forwarded to the Office of the Mayor of the municipality of Magdalena, Laguna. Written request was also sent to WHO Group to request for access to use the WHOQOL-BREF Filipino version.

Upon receipt of approval to conduct study and access to the instrument, pretesting of the instrument was conducted by administering the questionnaire to 10 mother grantees from the municipality of Liliw, immediately adjacent to Magdalena. These mother grantees were selected based on their availability and convenience in coordination with their assigned municipal link. This step was undertaken in order to gather clues about the success of the preferred method and the ways in which the chosen tools for the selected respondents can be strengthened and modified for the research process. During this time, any part of the instrument that appeared unclear to the respondents were noted along with their suggestions on how to make the instrument more appropriate and easier to understand. Upon integration of all the comments gathered, the instrument was revised and submitted for review and approval of the research panel members and ERB prior to actual data collection procedure.

After the finalization of the research instrument, research assistants were employed and given formal orientation as to the scope of their work. They were tasked

to approach the respondents individually during their vacant hours and administer the research instrument through an interview. In order to maximize the time needed for this study, data collection was conducted after the Family Development Session (FDS) or other meetings of the mother-grantees. Virtual platform such as messenger were also utilized as instructed by Regional Office. On the other hand, since some of the respondents requested to participate in the research at a later time or other location, such request was accepted. Informed consent was secured prior to data collection and the respondents' right to withdraw from participating in this research at any point of its conduct was honored.

Statistical treatment

In order to answer the stated research problems, the following statistical tools were employed:

1. Frequency and percentage were used to determine the profile of the respondents such as their age, educational attainment and duration of membership to CCT program.
2. Weighted mean was utilized to present the respondents' extent of compliance to program conditions in terms of attendance to FDS, health monitoring of 0-5 years old children, deworming of elementary children, attendance to school of 3-18 years old children and participation to community activities.
3. Weighted mean was also employed to determine the respondents' level of quality of life in terms of physical health, psychological health, social relationships and environment.

4. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was run to reveal if significant difference exists in the level of quality of life of the respondents in terms of their profile.
5. Independent t-test was utilized to determine if there is significant difference in the level of quality of life of compliant and non-compliant respondents.

Ethical Consideration

In the conduct of this investigation, the respondents were considered the most essential element. Hence, they were accorded the most proper treatment by safeguarding their rights. Informed consent was sought properly by the research assistants in a place that was convenient to the respondent such as their house or the venue of the conduct of their monthly FDS. Specifically, it was emphasized that participation in this study is voluntary in nature and that they can withdraw at any point of its conduct. They were not forced or coerced by any manner just to gain their participation. They were also encouraged to ask questions or concerns during the process of obtaining their consent.

Secondly, information pertinent to this research undertaking such as but not limited to its objectives, scope and delimitations and methodology were disclosed and discussed. Relevant questions were accommodated to enrich their understanding. Moreover, the respondents' level of understanding and competence to comprehend the questions to be thrown at them during the interview were assessed in order to elicit responses that are truly representative of their perceptions and opinions. Freedom from exploitation was likewise maintained by assuring them that the information they shared will not be used against them. Throughout the conduct of this study, guidelines stipulated in the Data Protection Act of 2012 were strictly observed. Toward this end,

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these provisions were explicitly stated in a written consent form duly signed by the respondents.

In addition, confidentiality of all the data collected was ensured at all times. Codes were assigned to the respondents in order to ensure their anonymity. This measure helped in protecting the dignity of the respondents regardless of their answers in the tools administered. They were also informed that the data gathered were only viewed and discussed by the primary investigator, research assistants, adviser and panel members. The university ERB may also view the records for verification. Further, since the scope of work of the research assistants was limited on the collection of data, they were not allowed to bring home the forms and reproduce a copy of it by any means. Accomplished forms were handed to the primary investigator on a daily basis. Proper safekeeping of the retrieved forms was always maintained by storing these documents in a locked cabinet. The electronic data and softcopy of reports were likewise password-protected. Moreover, the respondents were informed about the possibility of publishing the study in the future among various platforms including online journal and printed research articles without prejudice to their identities and privacy.

Cultural sensitivity and respect were conveyed all throughout the conduct of data collection. Moreover, in order not to affect their daily routine especially on their livelihood activities, data collection was performed during their free time. During the orientation, it was emphasized that no any monetary compensation or gift will be given in exchange of their participation to this study. Finally, in the preparation of the research report, proper citation of literatures and other sources used was properly rendered. Rest assured that there was no intentional failure to cite any scholarly work

used as reference source or material.

Chapter IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter presents and analyzes the data gathered in this study. The findings are presented based on the statements of the problems of the study.

Figure 2. Profile of the respondents with regards to Age

With 152 compliant Mother on a Conditional Cash Transfer Program, the ages “36 to 50 years old” have the highest frequency of one hundred and one (101) or 66.45% of the respondents. Followed by the ages “51 to 60 years old” with a frequency of twenty-five (25) or 16.45% of the respondents. While the ages “19-35 years old” have the least number of zero (18) or 11.84% of the respondents. This means that majority of the ages of the compliant Mother on a Conditional Cash Transfer Program during the time of the study are ranging 36 to 50 years old, which is more than half of the respondents.

And with 151 non-compliant Mother on a Conditional Cash Transfer Program, the ages “36 to 50 years old” have the highest frequency of eighty-four (84) or 55.63%

of the respondents. Followed by the ages “51 to 60 years old” with a frequency of thirty-four (34) or 22.52% of the respondents. While the ages “18 years old and below” have no response. This means that majority of the ages of the non-compliant Mother on a Conditional Cash Transfer Program during the time of the study are ranging 36 to 50 years old, which is more than half of the respondents.

With a total of 303 compliant and non-compliant Mother on a Conditional Cash Transfer Program, the ages “36 to 50 years old” have the highest frequency of one hundred eighty-five (185) or 61.06% of the total respondents. Followed by the ages “51 to 60 years old” with a frequency of fifty-nine (59) or 19.47% of the total respondents. While the ages “19 to 35 years old” have the least number of total 39 respondents or 12.87%. This means that majority of the ages of the compliant and non-compliant Mother on a Conditional Cash Transfer Program during the time of the study are ranging 36 to 50 years old or in their middle-age level and which is more than half of the total respondents.

Figure 3. Profile of the respondents with regards to Civil Status

With 152 compliant Mother on a Conditional Cash Transfer Program, the civil status *“Married”* have the highest frequency of one hundred thirteen (113) or 74.34% of the respondents. Followed by the civil status *“Single”* with a frequency of twenty-six (26) or 17.11% of the respondents. While the civil status *“Separated”* have the least number of three (3) or 1.97% of the respondents. This means that majority of the civil status of the compliant Mother on a Conditional Cash Transfer Program during the time of the study are married, which is almost three-fourths of the respondents.

And with 151 non-compliant Mother on a Conditional Cash Transfer Program, the civil status *“Married”* have the highest frequency of one hundred and eight (108) or 71.52% of the respondents. Followed by the civil status *“Single”* with a frequency of thirty-four (34) or 22.52% of the respondents. While the civil status *“Separated”* have least number of one (1) or 0.66% of the respondents. This means that majority of the civil status of the non-compliant Mother on a Conditional Cash Transfer Program during the time of the study are married which is more than half of the respondents.

With a total of 303 compliant and non-compliant Mother on a Conditional Cash Transfer Program, the civil status *“Married”* have the highest frequency of two hundred twenty-two (222) or 73.27% of the total respondents. Followed by the civil status *“Single”* with a frequency of sixty (60) or 19.80% of the respondents. While the civil status *“Separated”* have the least number of four (4) or 1.32% of the total respondents. This means that majority of the civil status of the compliant and non-compliant Mother on a Conditional Cash Transfer Program during the time of the study are married and which is more than half of the total respondents.

Figure 4. Profile of the respondents with regards to Educational Attainment

With 152 compliant Mother on a Conditional Cash Transfer Program, the educational attainment “*High School Graduate*” have the highest frequency of ninety (90) or 59.21% of the respondents. Followed by the educational attainment “*Elementary Graduate*” with a frequency of fifty-four (54) or 35.53% of the respondents. While the “*No Education*” have no respondents. This means that majority of the educational attainment of the compliant Mother on a Conditional Cash Transfer Program during the time of the study are high school graduate, which is more than half of the respondents.

And with 151 non-compliant Mother on a Conditional Cash Transfer Program, the educational attainment “*High School Graduate*” have the highest frequency of seventy-seven (77) or 50.99% of the respondents. Followed by the educational attainment “*Elementary Graduate*” with a frequency of seventy (70) or 46.36% of the respondents. While the “*No Education*” have no respondent. This means that majority of the educational attainment of the non-compliant Mother on a Conditional Cash Transfer Program during the time of the study are high school graduate which is more

than half of the respondents.

With a total of 303 compliant and non-compliant Mother on a Conditional Cash Transfer Program, the educational attainment *“High School Graduate”* have the highest frequency of one hundred sixty-seven (167) or 55.12% of the total respondents. Followed by the educational attainment *“Elementary Graduate”* with a frequency of one hundred twenty-four (124) or 40.92% of the respondents. While the *“College Graduate”* have the least number of twelve (12) or 3.96 % of the total respondents. This means that majority of the educational attainment of the compliant and non-compliant Mother on a Conditional Cash Transfer Program during the time of the study are high school graduate which is more than half of the total respondents.

Figure 5. Profile of the respondents with regards to No. of years in the Program

With 152 compliant Mother on a Conditional Cash Transfer Program, the number of years in the program *“7 years and below”* have the highest frequency of one hundred eleven (111) or 73.03% of the respondents. Followed by the number of years in the program *“8 to 10 years”* with a frequency of forty-one (41) or 26.97% of

the respondents While the number of years in the program “11 years and above” have the least number of frequency of one (1) or 0.66% of the respondents This means that majority of the number of years in the program of the compliant Mother on a Conditional Cash Transfer Program during the time of the study are ranging 6 years and below, which is almost three-fourths of the respondents.

And with 151 non-compliant Mother on a Conditional Cash Transfer Program, the number of years in the program “7 years and below” have the highest frequency of one hundred seventeen (117) or 77.48% of the respondents. Followed by the number of years in the program “8 to 10 years” with a frequency of thirty-four (34) or 22.52% of the respondents While the number of years in the program “11 years and above” have no response. This means that majority of the number of years in the program of the non-compliant Mother on a Conditional Cash Transfer Program during the time of the study are ranging 6 years and below, which is more than three-fourths of the respondents.

With a total of 303 compliant and non-compliant Mother on a Conditional Cash Transfer Program, the number of years in the program “7 years and below” have the highest frequency of two hundred twenty-eight (228) or 75.25% of the total respondents. Followed by the number of years in the program “8 to 10 years” with a frequency of seventy-five (75) or 24.75% of the total respondents While the number of years in the program “11 years and above” have the least number of frequency of one (1) or 0.33% of the total respondents This means that majority of the number of years in the program of the compliant and non-compliant Mother on a Conditional Cash Transfer Program during the time of the study are 6 years and below which is more than three-fourths of the total respondents.

Figure 6. Profile of the respondents with regards to Current Health Condition

With 152 compliant Mother on a Conditional Cash Transfer Program, the health condition “*without disease*” have the highest frequency of one hundred twenty (120) or 78.95% of the respondents. While the health condition “*with disease*” have the least number of thirty-two (32) or 21.05% of the respondents. This means that majority of the health condition of the compliant Mother on a Conditional Cash Transfer Program during the time of the study have no disease, which is more than three-fourths of the respondents.

And with 151 non-compliant Mother on a Conditional Cash Transfer Program, the health condition “*without disease*” have the highest frequency of one hundred twenty (120) or 79.47% of the respondents. While the health condition “*with disease*” have the least number of thirty-one (31) or 20.53% of the respondents. This means that majority of the health condition of the non-compliant Mother on a Conditional Cash Transfer Program during the time of the study have no disease, which is more than three-fourths of the respondents.

With a total of 303 compliant and non-compliant Mother on a Conditional Cash Transfer Program, the health condition “without disease” have the highest frequency of two hundred forty (240) or 79.21% of the respondents. While the health condition “with disease” have the least number of sixty-three (63) or 20.79% of the respondents. This means that majority of the health condition of the compliant and non-compliant Mother on a Conditional Cash Transfer Program during the time of the study have no disease, which is more than three-fourths of the respondents.

Table 1

Level of Quality of Life of the Respondents in terms of Physical Health

<i>Statements</i>	Compliant Group		Non-Compliant Group	
	<i>N = 152</i>		<i>N = 151</i>	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
To what extent do you feel that physical pain prevents you from doing what you need to do?				
<i>Hanggang saang punto mo nararamdaman na ang pisikal na sakit ay hinahadlangan kang gawin ang mga bagay na dapat mong gawin?</i>	3.50	.86	3.42	.93
How much do you need any medical treatment to function in your daily life?				
<i>Gaano mo kakailangan ang gamot o atensyong medikal para makakilos ka sa pang araw-araw mong pamumuhay?</i>	3.58	.97	3.49	.99

Do you have enough energy for everyday life? <i>Mayroon ka bang sapat na lakas sa iyong pang araw-araw na pamumuhay?</i>	3.55	.90	3.42	.91
How well are you able to get around? <i>Gaano ka kagaling sa pakikisalamuha?</i>	3.48	0.88	3.35	0.90
How satisfied are you with your sleep? <i>Gaano ka kakuntento sa kalidad ng iyong pagtulog?</i>	3.43	0.75	3.23	0.73
How satisfied are you with your ability to perform your daily living activities? <i>Gaano ka kakuntento sa iyong abilidad na gampanan ang pang araw-araw mong pamumuhay?</i>	3.51	0.65	3.30	0.70
How satisfied are you with your capacity for work? <i>Gaano ka kakuntento sa iyong kakayahan para iyong hanapbuhay?</i>	3.38	0.76	3.22	0.75
Overall Mean = 3.44	3.49	.82	3.35	.84
Standard Deviation =3.83				

Table 1 above shows the level of quality of life of the respondents in terms of physical health as revealed by the World Health Organization (WHO) QOL-BREF

questionnaire. The compliant group exhibited a high level of quality of life in terms of physical health while the non-compliant group demonstrated a fair level with weighted means of 3.49 and 3.35 respectively.

As evaluated by the compliant Mother on Physical health to a *great extent*, mostly they have enough energy for everyday life with ($M = 3.55, SD = 0.90$), satisfied with their ability to perform daily living activities with ($M = 3.51, SD = 0.65$), *mostly don't* need any medical treatment to function in their daily life with ($M = 3.58, SD = 0.97$), mostly are satisfied with ability to perform activities of daily living ($M = 3.51, SD = 0.65$), they are also satisfied with their ability to get around ($M = 3.48, SD = 0.88$) and mostly are contented with their sleep ($M = 3.43, SD = 0.75$). On the other hand, they reported a fair level of satisfaction with their capacity to work ($M = 3.38, SD = 0.76$).

As evaluated by the non-compliant Mother on Physical health to a *great extent*, mostly they have enough energy for everyday life with ($M = 3.42, SD = 0.93$), and mostly don't need any medical treatment to function in their daily life with ($M = 3.49, SD = .99$). On the other hand, they reported a fair level of satisfaction with their capacity to work ($M = 3.22, SD = 0.75$), satisfaction with ability to perform activities of daily living ($M = 3.30, SD = 0.70$), ability to get around with ($M = 3.35, SD = 0.90$) and satisfaction with their sleep ($M = 3.23, SD = 0.73$).

The compliant group exhibited a high level of quality of life in terms of physical health while the non-compliant group demonstrated a fair level with weighted means of 3.49 showing great extent and 3.35 showing moderately extent respectively.

The overall mean of 3.44, standard deviation of 0.83, indicates the level of quality of life of the respondents in terms of Physical Health are verbally interpreted as

great extent. The finding shows that the compliant and non-compliant Mother on Physical health during the time of the study partly adheres.

QoL is indeed multidimensional and to some extent subjective based on a person's life experiences (Jenkinson, n. d.). For instance, a healthy and happily married individual may suddenly report a low quality of life after suddenly losing job. By contrast, a person with disability who did not encounter significant challenges in the recent months may report a high quality of life despite his physical limitations. This conforms to the idea that QoL depends on various dimensions and not on single facet of life.

In the Philippines, individuals' perception of QoL is largely influenced by the changes encountered in the community that may include housing conditions, access to basic services such as water, electricity and shelter and programs that directly affect education and health. In the report published by Numbeo in 2018 about the QoL in the country, moderate QoL was noted when indices related to purchasing power, safety, healthcare, climate, cost of living, property price to income ratio, traffic commute time and pollution are accounted. Purchasing power, healthcare and property price to income ratio indices were reported to be very low, high and very high respectively. This means that majority of the households in the country are having difficulty to purchase their basic needs due to the rising prices of commodities and the relatively small number of wages they receive.

Table 2*Level of Quality of Life of the Respondents in terms of Psychological Health*

	Compliant Group N = 152		Non-Compliant Group N = 151	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
How much do you enjoy life? <i>Gaano kasiya-siya ang iyong pamumuhay?</i>	3.18	0.61	3.27	0.63
To what extent do you feel your life to be meaningful? <i>Gaano makabuluhan ang iyong pamumuhay?</i>	3.26	0.68	3.21	0.74
How well are you able to concentrate? <i>Gaano ka kahusay sa pagconcentrate?</i>	1.91	0.48	3.07	0.86
Are you able to accept your bodily appearance? <i>Tanggap mo ba ang iyong pisikal na kaanyuhan?</i>	4.03	1.06	4.04	1.06
How satisfied are you with yourself? <i>Gaano ka kakuntento sa iyong pagkatao?</i>	3.99	0.85	3.72	0.82
How often do you have negative feelings such as blue mood, despair, anxiety, depression? <i>Gaano ka kadalas makaramdam ng mga negatibong damdamin gaya ng pagkalungkot, kawalan ng pag-asa, pagkabalisa, at pag-aalala?</i>	3.02	0.76	2.87	0.74
Overall Mean = 3.29 Standard Deviation = .77	3.23	.74	3.36	.80

Table 2 above shows the level of quality of life of the respondents in terms of psychological health as revealed by the World Health Organization (WHO) QOL-BREF questionnaire. It shows that both the compliant and non-compliant groups demonstrated a fair level of quality of life in terms of psychological health, with the computed mean of compliant group slightly lower compared to the non-compliant group at 3.23 and 3.36 respectively.

As evaluated by the compliant Mother on psychological health to a *great extent*, mostly were able to accept their bodily appearance with ($M = 4.03, SD = 1.06$) and satisfied with themselves with ($M = 3.99, SD = 0.85$). Although also observed to *low extent*, the item with the lowest rating is with their ability to concentrate with ($M = 1.91, SD = 0.48$).

As evaluated by the non-compliant Mother on psychological health to a *great extent*, mostly were able to accept their bodily appearance with ($M = 4.04, SD = 1.06$) and satisfied with themselves with ($M = 3.72, SD = 0.82$). Although also observed to *low extent*, the item with the lowest rating with a moderate amount is their feeling on regarding their life that is meaningful ($M = 3.21, SD = 0.74$).

The data further reveals that both groups have high level of acceptance of their bodily appearance and satisfaction with themselves and fair level of feeling their lives to be meaningful and joyful and the frequency of having negative feelings such as blue mood, despair, anxiety, depression. Finally, the compliant group reported a low level of ability to concentrate compared to the fair level reported by the non-compliant group.

On the article of Manasi last December 2020, before COVID-19, he stated that anxiety and depression were the most common mental illnesses, affecting one in four people. Anxiety is affecting an increasing number of people, as noted in the article that

3–4 billion people have been put on lockdown as a COVID-19 mitigation response measure. According to the study, people are experiencing severe stress as a result of losing their jobs, unusual circumstances that cause them to be socially isolated and limited in their movement, and COVID-19-related deaths (within family and friends). In addition, being quarantined away from the safety of their homes and being suspected of having COVID-19 exposure cause stress and anxiety in many people.

As they conclude, factors affecting psychological state conditions determine the material conditions of the affected people who will be unable to sustain life and livelihoods in the context of a global pandemic. Current institutions and governance structures have shown to be a barrier to the poor in achieving the minimum material condition, making them increasingly vulnerable, marginalized, and sometimes even excluded from society. Extreme poverty puts weak and marginalized populations in a vulnerable and fragile psychological state.

Researchers Cho and colleagues found that low-income households suffered significant welfare losses as a result of the COVID-19 crisis and ECQ in their study, *Mitigating the Impact of COVID-19 on the Welfare of Low Income Households in the Philippines: The Role of Social Protection* (2020). In comparison to the nationally representative labor pool survey (LFS), which shows declines in employed ratios from 59 in October 2019 to 46 in April 2020, they claimed that the autumn is more significant. This may show that low-income households are more vulnerable to the utilization shock than other households.

The article's analysis of the decline found that it was particularly severe in urban and Luzon areas. As a result, the typical number of workdays per week also slightly decreased (5.3 to 5). As previously mentioned, the median daily wage for one worker

fell from PhP 280 to PhP 179, a 36 percent decrease. Additionally, the study found that almost half of all family businesses fail. Additionally, it revealed that 56 percent of households stated that at least one household member had skipped meals over the previous seven days due to a lack of food. Involuntary hunger, or going without food to eat, occurred in about 17% of Filipino families nationwide over the course of the previous three months, according to the Social Meteorological Observation Post's (SWS) nationwide pulse survey, which was conducted from May 4 to 10, 2020. This indicates that low-income households are much more likely to experience food insecurity.

These facts supported the studies on how COVID-19 may affect beneficiaries' psychological well-being because it had a significant impact on families' incomes, particularly those of low-income households. Their capacity for focus and enjoyment of life demonstrated acceptable results. Numerous factors related to the pandemic, including their income, the virus, the safety of their family, the bill, and other factors, may be the cause of their poor health-related quality of life scores on the psychological dimension. That explains why both non-compliant and compliant mothers benefited to a moderate extent from psychological health-related QOL.

Table 3

Level of Quality of Life of the Respondents in terms of Social Relationships

<i>Statements</i>	Compliant Group <i>N = 152</i>		Non-Compliant Group <i>N = 151</i>	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
How satisfied are you with your personal relationships? <i>Gaano ka kakuntento sa pakikisama at relasyon mo sa ibang tao?</i>	3.61	0.73	3.58	0.78

How satisfied are you with your sex life? <i>Gaano ka kakuntento sa iyong buhay pakikipagtalik?</i>	3.39	0.98	3.22	0.90
How satisfied are you with the support you get from your friends? <i>Gaano ka kakuntento sa mga suportang iyong natatanggap mula sa iyong mga kaibigan?</i>	3.46	0.85	3.33	0.80
Overall Mean = 3.43 Standard Deviation = .83	3.49	.85	3.38	.82

Table 3 above presents the level of quality of life of the respondents in terms of social relationships as revealed by the World Health Organization (WHO) QOL-BREF questionnaire. It shows that the compliant group reported a high level of quality of life in the aspect of social relationships compared to the fair level demonstrated by the non-compliant group with computed means of 3.49 and 3.38 respectively.

As evaluated by the compliant Mother on social relationships to a *great extent*, they are satisfied with their personal relationships with ($M = 3.61, SD = 0.73$) and satisfied with the support they get from their friends with ($M = 3.46, SD = 0.85$). Although also observed to *low extent*, the item with the lowest rating with neither satisfied nor dissatisfied they are satisfied with their sex life with ($M = 3.39, SD = 0.98$).

As evaluated by the non-compliant Mother on social relationships to a *great extent*, they are satisfied with their personal relationships with ($M = 3.58, SD = 0.78$) and satisfied with the support they get from their friends with ($M = 3.33, SD = 0.80$). Although also observed to *low extent*, the item with the lowest rating with neither satisfied nor dissatisfied they are satisfied with their sex life with ($M = 3.22, SD = 0.90$).

In overall, the compliant and non-compliant Mother on social relationships

showed a *great extent*, they are satisfied with their personal relationships with ($M = 3.59$, $SD = 0.75$) and satisfied with the support they get from their friends with ($M = 3.40$, $SD = 0.83$). Although also observed to *low extent*, the item with the lowest rating with neither satisfied nor dissatisfied they are satisfied with their sex life with ($M = 3.31$, $SD = 0.94$).

The overall mean of 3.43, standard deviation of 0.83, indicates the level of quality of life of the respondents in terms of Social Relationships are verbally interpreted as *great extent*. The finding shows that the compliant and non-compliant Mother on a social relationship during the time of the study perceives.

According to the "Family Stress Model," experiencing poverty is one of the more significant factors that can severely strain marriages, lead to depressive symptoms, and worsen family dysfunction (Conger et al. 2000). According to the "Family Stress Model," family dysfunction and emotional distress, such as depression, are caused by family. A sophisticated idea that includes inadequate supervision, a lack of control over the behavior of the child, a lack of support, being inconsistent, and aggression or hostility by parents or older siblings is that family distress leads to problems in the relationships between adults that are, in turn, linked to less effective parenting.

Based on Klebanov's study, which was based on a discussion of Wilson's (1996) hypotheses about parenting norms, patterns, and expectations for family life, and consequently the prospect structures in areas with high rates of poverty and unemployment. It was also stated in the article that a measure used for maternal social support, which might be a key indicator of mothers' functional access to socially embedded resources, combined mothers' access to an honest range of resources.

Net of other maternal, family, and neighborhood attributes, their study also

found that social support was significantly associated with neighborhood factors but had little impact on child outcomes. Table 4 below shows the respondents' environmental quality of life as determined by the World Health Organization (WHO) QOL-BREF questionnaire. In terms of the environmental aspect, it can be concluded that both groups reported a fair level of quality of life, with the computed means of the non-compliant group being marginally higher than those of the compliant group at 3.16 and 3.12, respectively.

Table 4

Level of Quality of Life of the Respondents in terms of Environment

<i>Statements</i>	Compliant Group <i>N = 152</i>		Non-Compliant Group <i>N = 151</i>	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
How safe do you feel in your daily life? <i>Gaano ka kaligtas sa pang araw-araw mong pamumuhay?</i>	3.03	0.52	3.17	0.79
How healthy is your physical environment? <i>Gaano kasagana ang iyong pisikal na kapaligiran?</i>	3.05	0.61	3.21	0.73
Do you have enough money to meet your needs? <i>Mayroon ka bang sapat na pera para sa iyong pang araw araw na pangangailangan?</i>	2.71	0.69	2.86	0.99
How available to you is the information that you need in your day-to-day life? <i>Gaano ka kasapat ang mga impormasyon na iyong kailangan para sa pang araw-araw mong pamumuhay?</i>	3.09	0.69	3.16	0.84
To what extent do you have the opportunity for leisure activities?	2.91	0.78	2.92	0.98

Gaano ka kadalas magkaron ng pagkakataon para maglibang?

How satisfied are you with the conditions of your living place? 3.55 0.88 3.40 0.88

Gaano ka kakuntento sa kalagayan ng lugar na iyong tinitirahan?

How satisfied are you with your access to health services? 3.61 0.81 3.48 0.89

Gaano ka kakuntento sa inyong serbisyong pangkalusugan?

How satisfied are you with your transport? 3.00 0.82 3.11 0.88

Gaano ka kakuntento sa iyong transportasyon?

Overall Mean = 3.13 3.11 .72 3.16 .87
Standard Deviation =.79

Table 4 above presents the level of quality of life of the respondents in terms of environment as revealed by the World Health Organization (WHO) QOL-BREF questionnaire.

As evaluated by the compliant Mother on environment to a *great extent*, they are satisfied with their access to health services with ($M = 3.61, SD = 0.81$) and satisfied with the conditions of their living place with ($M = 3.55, SD = 0.88$). Although also observed to *low extent*, the item with the lowest rating with moderately they have enough money to meet their needs with ($M = 2.71, SD = 0.69$).

As evaluated by the non-compliant Mother on environment to a *great extent*, they are satisfied with their access to health services with ($M = 3.48, SD = 0.89$) and they are satisfied with the conditions of their living place with ($M = 3.40, SD = 0.88$). Although also observed to *low extent*, the item with the lowest rating with moderately they have enough money to meet their needs with ($M = 2.86, SD = 0.99$).

The overall mean of 3.13, standard deviation of 0.79, indicates the level of quality of life of the respondents in terms of Environment are verbally interpreted as *moderately extent*. The finding shows that the compliant and non-compliant Mother on an environment during the time of the study partly distinguishes.

Specifically, both groups reported a high level of satisfaction with their access to health services and the condition of their living place. This finding may be attributed to the fact that the *Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps)* continuously ensures that health services are readily available and accessible to all beneficiaries of the program through the regular conduct of supply side assessment. Similarly, both groups reported a fair level of feeling safe in their everyday living, having a healthy physical environment, having enough money to meet their basic needs, availability of information needed in day-to-day living, opportunity for leisure activities and satisfaction with their transport condition. Similarly, these findings are aligned to the objectives of 4Ps of ensuring that these families are supplemented with cash grants that can be utilized for purchasing basic necessities for the households such as food, clothing and medicine. In fact, the findings of the current study coincide with that of Frufonga (2015) who noted that the expenditure pattern of poor families belonging to the conditional cash transfer program typically includes allocating the largest amount of their financial assistance for basic needs such as food, education and medicine or hospitalization, thereby keeping their members healthy and well.

Moreover, the conduct of FDS encourages them to maintain a healthy and sound environment through clean-up drives and community gardening and promote healthy family relations through a balance between work and leisure. Finally, these households are also encouraged to become active members of the society by

obtaining relevant information from government offices and relevant sources that affect their daily living.

Table 5

Significant Difference in the Quality of Life of the Respondents with respect to their Profile

Quality of Life	p-value
Age	0.0020
Civil Status	0.0057
Educational Attainment	0.0416
Number of years in the program	0.0516

Table 5 on the previous page shows the significant difference in the quality of life of the respondents with respect to their profile such as age, civil status, educational attainment, and number of years in the program. The data were statistically treated by using t-test and analysis of variance. From the data displayed, it can be gleaned that the quality of life of the respondents is significantly different with respect to their age, civil status and educational attainment since the computed p-values of 0.002, 0.0057 and 0.0416 respectively are lower than the alpha level of 0.05. On the other hand, the computed p-value of 0.0516 for the number of years in the program is higher than the alpha level of 0.05 which means that this variable is not statistically significant.

Based on these findings, this study partially accepts the research hypothesis stated. Specifically, this study implies that the quality of life of the mother-grantees in the conditional cash transfer program varies significantly depending on their age, civil status and educational attainment. However, it can be deduced that their quality of life

remains the same regardless of the number of years of their membership in the said program.

Table 6

Extent of Compliance of the Respondents to Program Conditions

Program Condition	Compliant Group <i>N = 152</i>	Non-Compliant Group <i>N = 151</i>
Attendance to Family Development Session (FDS)	94.22%	88.31%
Periodic health monitoring of 0-5 years old children	100%	100%
Deworming of children at the elementary level	100%	100%
Attendance to school of 3-18 years old children	86.13%	70.25%
Participation to community activities	95.5%	87.41%

Table 6 above shows the extent of compliance of the respondents to the conditions of the programs such as attendance to Family Development Session (FDS), periodic health monitoring of 0-5 years old children, deworming of children at the elementary level, attendance to school of 3-18 years old children and participation to community activities from January 2016 to January 2019.

The 152 compliant Mother have a record of 100.00% in “*Health Monitoring of 0 to 5 years old*” and “*Deworming of elementary children*”. Followed by 94.22% record in “*Attendance in Family Development Session*”. While the “*Education compliance of 3-18 years old*” interpreted as have the lowest record of 86.13% and they are all interpreted as *very great extent*. About 95.5% of the group was also able to actively participate to community activities conducted from January 2016 to January 2019

which mainly focused on maintaining a healthy and safe community through clean-up drives and community gardening.

For 151 non-compliant mother they also have a record of 100.00% in “*Health Monitoring of 0 to 5 years old*” and “*Deworming of elementary children*”. Followed by 88.31% record in “*Attendance in Family Development Session*”. While the “*Education compliance of 3-18 years old*” have the lowest record of 70.25% and they are all interpreted as *great extent*. However, a lower compliance rate in terms of attendance to FDS, participation to community activities and attendance to school of 3-18 years old children was recorded when compared to the compliant group.

With a total of 303 compliant and non-compliant mother and interpreted as *very great extent.*, they average of 100.00% in “*Health Monitoring of 0 to 5 years old*” and “*Deworming of elementary children*”. Followed by the average 91.27% record in “*Attendance in Family Development Session*” Some of beneficiaries were unable to attend the sessions due to conflict in livelihood and some attend personal matters. While the “*Education compliance of 3-18 years old*” have the lowest average record of 78.19% because of to lack of income of the parents, early pregnancy and forced to help to gain income to support the family.

This means that the extent of compliance of the respondents to program conditions with respect to attendance to Family Development Session, periodic health monitoring of 0-5 years old children, deworming of elementary children, attendance to school of 3-18 years old children is still very evident.

In the context of CCT programs, Ibararan and his colleagues (2017) defined conditionalities as “behaviors that favor the accumulation of human capital in the children of beneficiary households, thereby increasing their ability to generate income

in the future and help break the intergenerational transmission of poverty” (p. 35). This implies that beneficiaries become motivated to engage in certain behavioral changes before the cash transfers can be facilitated (Son, 2008). Hence, compliance to these conditions is one fundamental factor for the program to attain its short-term objective of increasing the capacity of households to purchase needed goods and services and long-term objective of human capital formation by investing particularly on children’s knowledge and skills through sound education (Rawlings & Rubio, 2003).

Table 7

Significant Difference in the Quality of Life of the Compliant and Non-Compliant Mothers

		Quality of Life		p-value	
		Physical health		0.0000	
		Psychological health		0.0144	
		Social relationships		0.0002	
		Environment		0.0002	

Health Related QOL	Compliant Mean	SD	VI	Non compliant Mean	VI
Physical	3.49	0.82	Great Extent Moderately	3.35	0.84
Psychological	3.23	0.74	Extent	3.36	0.8
Social	3.49	0.85	Great Extent Moderately	3.38	0.82
Environment	3.11	0.72	Extent	3.16	0.87

Table 7 shows the significant difference in the quality of life of the respondents in terms of their compliance. The data were statistically treated by using t-test and analysis of variance.

From the data presented, it can be seen that the quality of life of the respondents across all aspects is significantly different when their extent of compliance is considered. Specifically, the computed p-values of 0.0000, 0.0144, 0.0002 and 0.0002 for physical health, psychological health, social relationships and environmental aspect of quality of life respectively are all lower than the alpha level of 0.05. Therefore, this study accepts the research hypothesis stated. This further implies that the quality of life of the mother-grantees in the conditional cash transfer program varies significantly when their extent of compliance to various conditions of the program is considered.

Chapter V

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary of findings based on data presented and analyzed, the conclusions drawn and the recommendations offered.

Summary of Findings

Based on the analysis and interpretation of data gathered, the findings are summarized as follows:

1. In terms of the profile of the respondents, majority of the mother-grantees are of age 36-50 years old, finished high school, married and are active members of the conditional cash transfer program for no more than 7 years. A similar frequency distribution was observed when the respondents are grouped based on their extent of compliance.
2. Majority of the respondents reported that they have no disease/illness when they were asked about their current health condition during the data-gathering period of the study.
3. When it comes to the extent of compliance of the respondents to the conditions of the program, the compliant group reported a very great extent in terms of attendance to FDS, periodic health monitoring of 0-5 years old children, deworming of children at the elementary level and participation to community activities while demonstrating a great extent in terms of compliance to attendance to school of 3-18 years old children. On the other hand, the non-complaint group reported a very great extent in terms of their compliance to periodic health monitoring of 0-5 years old children and deworming of children at the elementary level, great extent in terms of attendance to FDS and participation to community activities and less extent in terms of compliance to attendance to school of 3-18 years old children.
4. In terms of the level of quality of life, the compliant group was found to have a high

level in the physical health and social relationship aspects and a fair level in the psychological and environmental aspects. The non-compliant group on the other hand reported a fair level of quality of life across all four aspects assessed.

5. Based on the data gathered, this study found out that the quality of life of the mother-grantees in the conditional cash transfer program varies significantly depending on their age, civil status and educational attainment. Their number of years of membership in the program however was found to be not significant factor in the level of quality of the respondents.
6. The present study found out that there is a significant difference in the quality of life of the respondents in terms of their extent of compliance. Data further revealed that the compliant respondents possessed a higher level of quality of life compared to the non-compliant respondents.

Conclusions

Based on the summary of findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Periodic health monitoring of 0-5 years old children, deworming of children at the elementary level and participation to community activities are among the conditions of the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipin Program (4Ps) that are greatly complied by the beneficiaries. On the other hand, attendance to school of 3-18 years old children appears to be the condition where the extent of compliance needs to be improved on.
2. The number of years of membership in the conditional cash transfer program has little to no bearing when it comes to the members' level of quality of life, though the current findings may be considered inconclusive given the various limitations of the study.
3. As the extent of compliance of the beneficiaries to the program conditions increase, their level of quality of life in terms of the physical health, psychological health, social

relationships and environment also increase. This further means that as the program recipients faithfully adhere to the requisites of 4Ps, they are more likely to realize the importance of health promotion, educational investment and active community participation which ultimately contribute to their state of well-being and improved perceptions of their position in life.

Recommendations

Based on the findings gathered and conclusions draw in this study, the following are hereby recommended:

1. Monitoring of compliance of eligible children under the education component of the conditional cash transfer must be strengthened. Children with high reports of tardiness and absences may be reported by the teachers to the assigned Municipal Link so that timely and appropriate case management may be rendered in consonance with the schools' efforts of reducing drop-out rates.
2. Assessment of the program beneficiaries' level of quality of life using the WHO questionnaire or similar instrument may be considered during the program's regular household assessment as this assessment provides useful information that may help program implementers in crafting more responsive and evidence-based sets of interventions. This may be done as a rider questionnaire during the administration of the Social Welfare and Development Indicators (SWDI) as the concerned agency determines the impact of the program to their beneficiaries.
3. Modules of the Family Development Session (FDS) that specifically focus on the psychological aspect of living may be crafted since this was found out to be needing attention. Particularly, topics concerning life satisfaction and acceptance of oneself appear imperative especially during the time of a pandemic health situation. Toward this end, theories such as positive psychology and humanism may be tapped as

fundamental sources. Mental health awareness sessions are also highly suggested to further combat negative factors that confront vulnerable families such as those who belong to the poor sectors of the society.

4. Despite already having various FDS modules that concern on promoting healthy environment, program implementers may consider adding topics that center on general safety and transportation comfort as these items were found to be needing interventions. While such findings may be attributed to the COVID-19 health crisis during the conduct of the study, it may still be prudent to invest on interventions that capacitate beneficiaries during periods of unprecedented crisis. Teaching of good health practices and psychical defense practices may be considered.
5. For future researches that will investigate on the quality of life of recipients of a conditional cash transfer program like 4Ps, it is suggested that the number of respondents and setting of the study be increased to make the findings more conclusive. Especially in terms of determining the difference in the quality of life based on the membership tenure in the program, it would be better to have larger sample size to produce more accurate data and consequent interpretation.

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Appendices

APPENDIX A

Letter to DSWD

July 1, 2020

LUCIA C. ALMEDA

Regional Director-OIC

Department of Social Welfare and Development Field Office IV-A

Alabang, Muntinlupa City

Thru : **MILDRED L. MINA**
Social Welfare Officer IV / Provincial Link
Laguna Provincial Operations Office
Sta. Cruz, Laguna

Dear Director Almeda:

Greetings of Good Health to you!

I am Jenzer Mae A. Ambrocio, a Project Development Officer II (Municipal Link) assigned in the Municipality of Magdalena, Laguna. I am currently taking up Master of Arts in Nursing major in Maternal and Child Nursing at the University of the Philippines Open University. In the pursuit of knowledge and its contribution to healthcare and nursing profession, I am presently making my research study with the title “**Compliance to Program Conditions and Health-related Quality of Life of Mothers on Conditional Cash Transfer.**” This is a non-experimental study with an aim of establishing any correlation or relationship on the compliance of grantees with program conditions and their quality of life.

In this connection, may I humbly seek permission to conduct the study with select Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps) grantees in the Municipality of Magdalena. Rest assured that the data gathering procedure to be conducted by the research assistants will not take place during official 4Ps activities. Further, informed consent will be secured first among the targeted respondents. Ethical considerations and research principles will be strictly observed. Finally, may I also request for a copy of the compliance turnout raw data and beneficiary tracking report from January 2015 to January 2019 through the Compliance Verification System officers. It is with sincere assurance that all data and information will be treated with utmost confidentiality.

Enclosed in this letter is a copy of my research proposal for your further reference. If I can be of further assistance regarding this matter, I may be reached at mobile no. 09291150550 or via email at jenzer_ambrocio@yahoo.com. May this request merit your kind approval. Thank you.

Sincerely,

Jenzer Mae A. Ambrocio, RN

Researcher

Noted by:

Queenie R. Ridulme, RN, MAN

Research Mentor and Associate Professor

University of the Philippines Open University

APPENDIX B

Letter to Magdalena, Laguna Municipal Mayor

July 1, 2020

HON. DAVID O. AVENTURADO JR

Municipal Mayor
Magdalena, Laguna

Dear Mayor Aventurado:

Greetings of Good Health to you!

I am Jenzer Mae A. Ambrocio, a Project Development Officer II (Municipal Link) employed by the Department of Social Welfare and Development Field Office IV-A, assigned in the Municipality of Magdalena, Laguna. I am currently taking up Master of Arts in Nursing major in Maternal and Child Nursing at the University of the Philippines Open University. In the pursuit of knowledge and its contribution to healthcare and nursing profession, I am presently making my research study with the title “**Compliance to Program Conditions and Health-related Quality of Life of Mothers on Conditional Cash Transfer.**”

In this connection, it is my great privilege to inform your good office about the conduct of this study in your area of governance. This is a non-experimental study with an aim to know if there is a correlation between the compliance on program conditions and quality of life of mothers on Conditional Cash Transfer, popularly known as the *Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program* (4Ps). During the data collection procedure, there will be research assistants that will conduct interviews among selected mother-grantees during their vacant hours. **This data collection phase is set to run from May to June 2020.** They will be provided with identification cards for this purpose. Rest assured that ethical considerations and research principles will be strictly observed. Further, informed consent will be secured first among the targeted respondents.

Enclosed in this letter is a copy of my research proposal for your further reference. If I can be of further assistance regarding this matter, I may be reached at mobile no. 09291150550 or via email at jenzer_ambrocio@yahoo.com. May this request merit your kind approval. Thank you.

Sincerely,

Jenzer Mae A. Ambrocio, RN

Researcher

Noted by:

Queenie R. Ridulme, RN, MAN

Research Mentor and Associate Professor
University of the Philippines Open University

Appendix C

Permission Letter to use WHOQOL-BREF

July 1, 2020

The World Health Organization

20 Avenue Appia

1211 Geneva 27, Switzerland

Publications Email: permission@who.int

Dear Sir / Madame:

Greetings of Good Health to you!

I am Jenzer Mae A. Ambrocio, a development worker in the Philippines, employed by the Department of Social Welfare and Development under the *Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps)*, the country's flagship poverty-reduction program in the form of a conditional cash transfer (CCT). I am currently taking up Master of Arts in Nursing major in Maternal and Child Nursing at the University of the Philippines Open University. In the pursuit of knowledge and its contribution to healthcare and nursing profession, I am presently making my research study with the title "**Compliance to Program Conditions and Health-related Quality of Life of Mothers on Conditional Cash Transfer.**"

In this connection, I would like to seek permission to use the World Health Organization Quality of Life (WHOQOL-BREF) questionnaire English version and translate it to Filipino, the national language of the Philippines since the respondents of this study come from the poor sectors of the society. This is a non-experimental study with an aim of establishing any correlation or relationship between the compliance of grantees with program conditions and their quality of life. Rest assured that ethical considerations and research principles will be properly observed in the use of this instrument.

Enclosed in this letter is a copy of my research proposal for your further reference. If I can be of further assistance regarding this matter, I may be reached at mobile no. 09291150550 or via email at jenzer_ambrocio@yahoo.com. May this request merit your kind approval. Thank you.

Sincerely,

Jenzer Mae A. Ambrocio, RN

Researcher

Noted by:

Queenie R. Ridulme, RN, MAN

Research Mentor and Associate Professor

University of the Philippines Open University

Appendix D

Kaalamang Pahintulot

KAALAMANG PAHINTULOT

Naiintindihan ko na isa itong pag-aaral kaugnay sa kalidad ng buhay ng mga ina na nabibilang sa Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino *Program* (4Ps) at mahalaga ang resulta ng pag-aaral na ito hindi lamang sa mga miyembro ng 4Ps kundi pati na rin sa *Local Government Unit, Department of Social Welfare and Development, Department of Health* at iba pang ahensiya ng gobyerno dahil maaaring magbigay daan ang resulta ng pag-aaral upang mas mapabuti pa ang implementasyon ng programa at magdagdag pa ng mga hakbangin upang makatulong sa mas maraming tao.

Naiintindihan ko rin na:

1. Dadaan ako sa proseso ng pagsisiyasat at magiging kuwalipikado lamang ako sa pag-aaral kung natugunan ko ang lahat ng inaasahang pamantayan.
2. Napili ako na maging kalahok dahil ako ay isang benipisyaryo ng Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino *Program* sa bayan ng Magdalena.
3. Hindi inaasahan na ang pag-aaral na ito ay hahantong sa pisikal o emosyonal na panganib.
4. Mahigpit at kumpidensyal ang impormasyong aking ibabahagi at bibigyan ng *code* ang datos para sa palatandaan ng mga indibidwal na kalahok upang hindi makilala.
5. Handa ang buod ng mga resulta sakaling hilingin ko na makita.

Kinikilala ko na:

Nabigyan ako ng pagkakataon na magtanong tungkol sa pag-aaral na ito ng pananaliksik, at sinagot ang mga katanungang nang maayos.

Sa pagbibigay ng aking pahintulot, naunawaan ko na kusang-loob ang aking paglahok sa pag-aaral na ito at maaari kong bawiin anumang oras gamit ang impormasyon na ibinigay ni Ms Jenzer Mae A. Ambrocio, RN, kung kinakailangan.

Pinapahintulutan ko ang tagapagsuri na ilabas ang impormasyon na nakuha sa pag-aaral na ito sa mga siyentipikong pag-aaral. Batid ko na hindi ako makikilala sa pangalan.

Nabigyan ako ng mga numero ng telepono ng mananaliksik, si Ms. Jenzer Mae A. Ambrocio, RN at maaari siyang kontakin anumang oras kung mayroon akong mga katanungan.

Pinapatunayan na nabasa at naiintindihan ko ang impormasyon sa itaas, at sumasang-ayon akong lumahok sa pag-aaral na ito.

Lagda ng Kalahok

Saksi

Petsa

Petsa

Consent Form

Quality of Life and Compliance Among Mothers ...

Ako si, _____, _____ na taong gulang, at kasalukuyang naninirahan sa bayan ng Magdalena, Laguna, ay nagsasaad na nabasa at naintindihan kong mabuti ang mga nakapaalob sa pahayag na ito. Lahat ng impormasyon ay malinaw at aking napagalaran. Ito ay nagpapatunay na nakatanggap ako ng kopya ng pahayag na ito. Ako ay sumasangayon sa pagiging parte ng pagaaral na ito.

Pirma ng *Respondent*

Lagda sa ibabaw ng Pangalan

Pahayag ng tagapanaliksik/kukuha ng impormasyon

Binasa at inaral ko ang mga impormasyon na nakasulat na inilathala ng *respondent* at nakakasisigurong naintindihan at napagalaran niya ang mga nakasaad dito.

Ito ay patunay na hindi pinilit at ito'y kusang loob na inaprubahan ng *respondent*.

Pirmaa ng tagapanaliksik/kukuha ng impormasyon:

Lagda sa ibabaw ng Pangalan

Appendix E

WHO Questionnaire

I. Datos ng Benepisyaryo ng Pantawid (Demographic Profile):

Pangalan (Name): _____

Kasarian (Sex): _____

Pinakamataas na antas na natapos sa pag-aaral (Highest Educational Attainment): _____

Elementarya Sekondarya Kolehiyo Hindi nakapag-aral

Edad (Age): _____

Katayuang-Sibil (Civil Status): _____

Bilang ng taon sa Programa (Number of Years in the program): _____

Ikaw ba ay may Karamdaman/Sakit? Oo Hindi

Kung Oo, ano ang iyong karamdaman o problema sa kalusugan?

Ang pagtatasang ito ay naglalayong malaman ang kalidad ng iyong buhay, kalusugan at iba pang bahagi ng iyong buhay. Sagutin ang mga katanungan. Kung hindi sigurado sa iyong kasagutan, maaaring pumili ng isa sa pinakaangkop na kasagutan, ito ang magsisilbi mong tugon. Mangyaring tandaan ang iyong mga pamantayan, pag-asa, kasiyahan at alalahanin. Hinihiling namin na muli mong balikan ang iyong buhay sa nagdaang dalawang linggo. Sa pag-alaala noong nagdaang dalawang linggo, narito ang maaaring halimbawang katanungan.

	Hindi	Hindi Masyado	Minsan	Mayroong suporta	Kumpletong suporta
	1	2	3	4	5
Nakakakuha ka ba ng suporta sa iba na iyong kailangan?					

Bilugan mo ang numero na nagpapakita kung gaanong suporta ang nakukuha mo sa iba nitong nakaraang dalawang linggo.

Basahin ang bawat katanungan, bilugan ang nararapat na sagot base sa iyong nararamdaman.						
		Sobrang hirap	Mahirap	Minsan mahirap minsan hindi	Mabuti	Napakaganda
1(G1)	Paano mo ire-rate ang kalidad ng iyong pamumuhay?	1	2	3	4	5
		Sobrang hindi nasisiyahan	Hindi Nasisiyahan	Minsan nasisiyahan minsan hindi	Nasisiyahan	Sobrang nasisiyahan

2 (G4)	Gaano ka kakuntento sa iyong kalusugan?	1	2	3	4	5
Ang mga sumusunod na katanungan ay nagtatanong tungkol sa kung gaano ka nakaranas ng mga ilang mga bagay sa huling dalawang lingo.						
		Hindi talaga	Konti	Katamtaman	Sobra	Sobrang tindi
3 (F1.4)	Hanggang saang punto mo nararamdaman na ang pisikal na sakit ay hinahadlangan kang gawin ang mga bagay na dapat mong gawin?	1	2	3	4	5
4(F11.3)	Gaano mo kakailangan ang gamot o atensyong medikal para makakilos ka sa pang araw-araw mong pamumuhay?	1	2	3	4	5
5(F4.1)	Gaano kasiya-siya ang iyong pamumuhay?	1	2	3	4	5
6(F24.2)	Gaano makabuluhan ang iyong pamumuhay?	1	2	3	4	5
		Hindi talaga	Konti	Katamtaman	Sobra	Lubha/Labis
7(F5.3)	Gaano ka kahusay sa pagconcentrate?	1	2	3	4	5
8 (F16.1)	Gaano ka kaligtas sa pang araw-araw mong pamumuhay?	1	2	3	4	5
9 (F22.1)	Gaano kasagana ang iyong pisikal na kapaligiran?	1	2	3	4	5
		Hindi talaga	Konti	Katamtaman	Madalas	Kumpleto
10 (F2.1)	Mayroon ka bang sapat na lakas sa iyong pang araw-araw na pamumuhay?	1	2	3	4	5
11 (F7.1)	Tanggap mo ba ang iyong pisikal na kaanyuhan?	1	2	3	4	5
12 (F18.1)	Mayroon ka bang sapat na pera para sa iyong pang araw araw na pangangailangan?	1	2	3	4	5
13 (F20.1)	Gaano ka kasapat ang mga	1	2	3	4	5

	impormasyon na iyong kailangan para sa pang araw-araw mong pamumuhay?					
14 (F21.1)	Gaano ka kadalas magkaron ng pagkakataon para maglibang?	1	2	3	4	5
15 (F9.1)	Gaano ka kagaling sa pakikisalamuha?	1	2	3	4	5
		Sobrang hindi nasisiyahan	Hindi Nasisiyahan	Minsan nasisiyahan minsan hindi	Nasisiyahan	Sobrang nasisiyahan
16 (F3.3)	Gaano ka kakuntento sa kalidad ng iyong pagtulog?	1	2	3	4	5
17 (F10.3)	Gaano ka kakuntento sa iyong abilidad na gampanan ang pang araw-araw mong pamumuhay?	1	2	3	4	5
18(F12.4)	Gaano ka kakuntento sa iyong kakayahan para iyong hanapbuhay?	1	2	3	4	5
19 (F6.3)	Gaano ka kakuntento sa iyong pagkatao?	1	2	3	4	5
20(F13.3)	Gaano ka kakuntento sa pakikisama at relasyon mo sa ibang tao?	1	2	3	4	5
21(F15.3)	Gaano ka kakuntento sa iyong buhay pakikipagtalik?	1	2	3	4	5
22(F14.4)	Gaano ka kakuntento sa mga suportang iyong natatanggap mula sa iyong mga kaibigan?	1	2	3	4	5
23(F17.3)	Gaano ka kakuntento sa kalagayan ng lugar na iyong tinitirahan?	1	2	3	4	5

24(F19.3)	Gaano ka kakuntento sa inyong serbisyong pangkalusugan?	1	2	3	4	5
25(F23.3)	Gaano ka kakuntento sa iyong transportasyon?	1	2	3	4	5
		Hindi	Bihira	Minsan	Madalas	Lagi
26 (F8.1)	Gaano ka kadalas makaramdam ng mga negatibong damdamin gaya ng pagkalungkot, kawalan ng pag-asa, pagkabalisa, at depresyon?	1	2	3	4	5

Appendix F

DSWD Endorsement

FOR : MS. LUCIA C. ALMEDA
OIC - REGIONAL DIRECTOR
DSWD Field Office IV-A

FROM : THE OIC - DIVISION CHIEF/ PO IV
Policy and Plans Division

SUBJECT : APPROVAL OF RESEARCH

DATE : OCTOBER 9, 2020

We are respectfully transmitting herewith for the OIC - Regional Director's approval the research of Ms. Jenzer Mae A. Ambrocio, a Master of Arts in Nursing, major in Maternal and Child Nursing student of UP Open University. She will interview Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program Beneficiaries (mother-grantees) in Magdalena, Laguna. For her data gathering, she will administer a survey to the said beneficiaries. The researcher is currently engaged with the Field Office as Project Development Office II (Municipal Link) of Magdalena, Laguna.

The Policy Development and Planning Section has reviewed his research and found it complying with the requirements set by Memorandum Circular (MC) No. 10, s. 2019. Hereunder are the relevant information taken from his proposal and that no revision (i.e., grammar, structure, sequence) was made as per guidelines:

Proponent/s	Jenzer Mae A. Ambrocio
Institution	UP Open University (Los Baños, Laguna)
Title/ Topic of Research Project	Quality of Life of Compliant and Non-compliant Mothers on a Conditional Cash Transfer Program in Magdalena, Laguna
Background of the Study	This study aims to determine the quality of life of compliant and non-compliant mothers under a conditional cash transfer program. It will also cover the moderating effects of the respondents' age, educational attainment, and duration of membership in the CCT program. Data collection procedure will be conducted from October to December 2020 in the municipality of Magdalena, Province of Laguna.
General & Specific Objective/s	This study aims to determine the quality of life of compliant and non-compliant mothers under a conditional cash transfer program. The study will seek answers to the following questions: 1. What is the extent of compliance of the respondents to program conditions with respect to: a. attendance to Family Development Session; b. periodic health monitoring of 0-5 years old children; c. deworming of elementary children; d. attendance to school of 3-18 years old children; and e. participation to community activities?

	<p>2. What is the level of quality of life of the respondents in terms of:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. physical health; b. psychological health; c. social relationships; and d. environment? <p>3. Is there a significant difference in the quality of life of the respondents with respect to their profile?</p> <p>4. Is there a significant difference in the quality of life of the respondents in terms of their compliance?</p>
Methodology	<p>This study will employ a comparative research design which “essentially compares two groups in an attempt to draw a conclusion about them” (Richardson, 2018). This method will help in establishing better understanding of the potential similarities and differences between the groups being studied.</p> <p>Specifically, a causal-comparative research method will be utilized in order to identify the relationship between the variables of the study or to determine whether the independent variable will cause changes on the dependent variable (Salkind, 2010).</p> <p>To meet the objectives of this study, a simple random sampling will be employed.</p>
Data/ Materials to be requested from the DSWD	<p>Compliance turnout raw data and beneficiary tracking report from January 2016 to January 2019 through the Compliance Verification System officers;</p> <p>List of latest Active Households</p>
Target Areas/ Sites	<p>Municipality of Magdalena, Laguna*</p> <p><i>*Pre-testing of tool in Liliw, Laguna (10 beneficiaries)</i></p>
Research Output	<p>This research study would like to determine the quality of life of its mother-beneficiaries specifically considering their extent of compliance to program conditions such as adherence to preventive health check-ups of children 5 years old and below and attendance to monthly Family Development Session. It will also cover the moderating effects of the respondents' age, educational attainment, and duration of membership in the CCT program. this study hopes to offer viable recommendations to improve the health-related quality of life of CCT beneficiaries.</p>
Ethical Considerations/ Guidelines Employed	<p>In the conduct of this investigation, the respondents will be considered the most essential element. Hence, they will be accorded the most proper treatment by safeguarding their rights. Informed consent will be sought properly by the research assistants in a place that is convenient to the respondent. Specifically, it will be emphasized that participation in this study is voluntary in nature and that they can withdraw at any point of its conduct. They will also be</p>

	encouraged to ask questions or concerns during the process of obtaining their consent.																																								
Project Timeline (Researchers may use a Gantt Chart to show the project timeline)	September to December 2020																																								
Budget & Fund Source *If applicable	<p>Source: <i>Own Capital</i></p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2">BUDGET REQUIREMENT</th> </tr> <tr> <th>Particulars</th> <th>Amount</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>A. MOOE</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>1. Contracted Service</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>1.1 Professional Services (Part-Time)</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>1.1.1 Research Assistant (50 pesos per hour to work for 80 hours)</td> <td>4,000</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1.1.2 Encoder (5 pesos per form/ research instrument x 300)</td> <td>1,500</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1.1.3 Consultant (entire engagement)</td> <td>10,000</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>1.2 Wages (Non-Regular Staff)</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>2. Travel</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>2.1 Transportation Allowance</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>2.1.1 Research Assistant (200 pesos per day x 10 days)</td> <td>2,000</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2.1.2 Principal Investigator (attendance to consultation sessions)</td> <td>4,000</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>3. Supplies</td> <td>1,500</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3.1 Printing and Photocopy of Research Instruments and other Related Documents</td> <td>500</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3.2 Interview Kits and IDs of Research Assistants</td> <td>500</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3.3 CDs for Presentation Copies</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	BUDGET REQUIREMENT		Particulars	Amount	A. MOOE		1. Contracted Service		1.1 Professional Services (Part-Time)		1.1.1 Research Assistant (50 pesos per hour to work for 80 hours)	4,000	1.1.2 Encoder (5 pesos per form/ research instrument x 300)	1,500	1.1.3 Consultant (entire engagement)	10,000			1.2 Wages (Non-Regular Staff)				2. Travel		2.1 Transportation Allowance		2.1.1 Research Assistant (200 pesos per day x 10 days)	2,000	2.1.2 Principal Investigator (attendance to consultation sessions)	4,000			3. Supplies	1,500	3.1 Printing and Photocopy of Research Instruments and other Related Documents	500	3.2 Interview Kits and IDs of Research Assistants	500	3.3 CDs for Presentation Copies	
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			2,000
	4. <i>Communication</i> (load allowance to cover cellular phone and Internet browsing)		
	5. <i>Miscellaneous/Sundries</i>		N.A.
	B. Equipment Overlay		2,600
	C. Overhead Cost (10-15% of the combined Personnel Services and MOOE)		n/a
			Total: 28,600
Data Analysis	<p>Statistical treatment</p> <p>In order to answer the stated research problems, the following statistical tools will be employed:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Frequency and percentage will be used to determine the profile of the respondents such as their age, educational attainment and duration of membership to CCT program. 2. Weighted mean will be utilized to present the respondents' extent of compliance to program conditions in terms of attendance to FDS, health monitoring of 0-5 years old children, deworming of elementary children, attendance to school of 3-18 years old children and participation to community activities. 3. Weighted mean will also be employed to determine the respondents' level of quality of life in terms of physical health, psychological health, social relationships and environment. 4. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) will be run to reveal if significant difference exists in the level of quality of life of the respondents in terms of their profile. 5. Independent t-test will be utilized to determine if there is significant difference in the level of quality of life of compliant and non-compliant respondents. 		

Further, considering that Ms. Ambrocio has complied with the research requirements set by the Department, we recommend that the approval of her request to conduct her data gathering on the most preferred time of her respondents.

For the OIC - Regional Director's approval.

EDEN M. ARCE

HMB/LDOF

Curriculum Vitae

JENZER MAE AMBROCIO

NURSE/ PUBLIC SERVANT

 Pagsanjan, Laguna
 09291150550
 jenzermæ@gmail.com

CAREER OVERVIEW

Provides care and support to patients in various healthcare settings. Involved in many aspects of patient care, including monitoring vital signs, administering medication and etc. Referral to different stakeholders. Help the families in improving their quality of life.

EDUCATION

Bachelor of Science in
Nursing

SKILLS

- Basic computer literacy skills
- Organizational skills
- Strategic planning and scheduling skills
- Time-management skills
- Nursing Skills
- Social Worker Skills

REFERENCE

Mildred L. Mina
SWO IV -DSWD Laguna
mildred_mina@yahoo.com

EXPERIENCE

DSWD IV-A Project Development Officer II

November 2012 - present

- Administer Social Welfare Development Indicator (House to house assessment to know the level of their well-being survival, subsistence, Self-sufficiency)
- Assist beneficiaries in some trainings conducted by partners in SLP, BUB, PSWDO, MSWDO, NGO and etc.
- Do home visitations and counseling if needed
- Refer beneficiaries to livelihood
- Refer and assist Families for Medical, Financial, Burial Assistance and etc to E-AICS or Expanded AICS
- Coordinate to partners in Department of Education, Department of Health, DILG, LGU offices and etc
- Coordinate and submit documents at Provincial Operations Office if needed